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PROJECT WORK DONE ON

**A STUDY OF MOTIVATIONAL FACTORS FOR THE CENTRAL
OFFICE EMPLOYEES OF KARNATAKA MILK FEDERATION
LIMITED BANGALORE**

DISSERTATION SUBMITTED TO ANNAMALAI UNIVERSITY,
IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS
FOR THE DEGREE OF

**MASTER OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION
(SELF MANAGEMANT AND CRISIS MANAGEMENT)**

Under the guidance of

Dr. S.JAYALAKSHMI

By

NAGESH.N.V

Enrolment Number: 8401100028

**DIRECTORATE OF DISTANCE EDUCATION
ANNAMALAI UNIVERSITY**

ANNAMALAI UNIVERSITY

ANNAMALAINAGAR

2013

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DECLARATION

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

“Gratitude is the language of heart. When the language is from the heart, emotions prevail and when emotions prevail word fails.”

It is a great pleasure for me to acknowledge the contribution and continued support of all the individuals for their efforts. I would hereby take the opportunity to express gratitude to people who have helped me directly and indirectly to accomplish this task.

First of all, my sincere gratitude to Supreme GOD Father SHIVA from the core of my heart for giving the golden opportunity to successfully present this dissertation

It is with real pleasure that, I record my indebtedness to my guide **Dr.S.jayalakshmi** M.A(Hindi), M.A(Sanskrit), B.Ed, Phd(Sanskrit), Sanskrit Scholar, Life skill Trainer & Consultant, Bangalore, for his counsel and guidance during the preparation of this dissertation.

Next, I would also like to thank **Mr. A.S Premanath**, Managing Director, Karnataka Milk Federation, Bangalore who has helped me in all respects for successful completion of this task on time .

This acknowledgment will be incomplete without the thanks of my parents and my brother who have extended all moral & spiritual support and encouraged me to accomplish the task on time.

My sincere thanks are due to **B.K.Bhagya**, Teacher In Charge, PBKIVV, Chickmagalur and **B.K.Pandiamani**, for their blessings and support to complete this MBA project successfully.

My thanks are due to all divine brothers and sisters of Prajapita Brahma Kumaris Ishwariya Vishwa Vidyalaya, at Mount Abu, Madurai Center and Chickmagalur Center, Karnataka for their whole hearted support ,co-operation and blessings to complete my dissertation successfully.

My Thanks are due to all my senior officers, colleagues, sub ordinates and friends of KMF, Bangalore , my relatives and all other persons who have directly and indirectly helped me in completion of this assignment

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With reference to the above subject, permission is hereby accorded to Mr. Nagesh NV, Deputy Director(D.T) to prepare project report on 'A study of Motivational Factors for Central Office Employees of KMF at KMF Central Office, Bangalore as a part of his MBA course under distance education programme of Annamalai University at his own cost. This permission is subjected to condition that, there will be no disturbances / hindrances to the day to day work of the unit and this project is only for academic purpose.

for Karnataka Milk Federation Ltd.,

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

At one time, employees were considered just another input into the production of goods and services. What perhaps changed this way of thinking about employees was research, referred to as the Hawthorne Studies conducted by Elton Mayo from 1924 to 1932. This study found employees are not motivated solely by money and employee behavior is linked to their attitudes. The Hawthorne Studies began the human relations approach to management, whereby the needs and motivation of employees become the primary focus of managers. For example, research suggests that as employees' income increases, money becomes less of a motivator. Also, as employees get older, interesting work becomes more of a motivator.

Human Resource Management has always been linked to human as the most important asset that drives the organization to success or failure (Pierce et. al., 2003; Torrington et. al., 2002). Man is said to be the most complex compared to the other three M, namely money, machine and material. Employees are the only resource that cannot be duplicated (Thomas, 2002). Whilst the other three M's has no feelings, man is ever changing coupled with its mood swing.

In organization, employers' concern for employee commitment is on the rise due to the high turnover and job-hopping culture which has been a major set-back for organization. In this era of talent-war, employers thrive to compensate with motivational factors to gain competitive advantage in building employee commitment. In returns, employee commitment will have positive impact on job satisfaction as well as productivity and minimize turnover.

Most employers realize that the road to success lies in motivated and commitment workforce who are highly efficient, productive, motivated and dedicated to the organization. Employers doubting thoughts on employee commitment in terms of loyalty to an organization seems unfair at times. In order to gain employee commitment, employers have to be pro-active in supporting initiatives energizing employees to move towards employee's commitment. Apart from monetary rewards, employers must create a win-win situation via envisage new approaches such as motivational factors to successfully gain employees commitment.

The imperative need of discovering, comprehending, and implementing employee motivation has been a principle concern for organizations, managers, and even first line supervisors because employee motivation has been and will be the deciding factor in work performance and in turn decide the success or failure of an organization. Consequently, considerable study and research of this topic has been conducted, and reasonable amounts of findings have been produced to benefit contemporary organizations and management. The study and research of this topic will continually be a major task for modern and prospect psychologists, Organizational Behavior (OB) researchers, and scholars from management and organizational related fields as long as the significance of employee motivation can affect an organizations' success.

The purpose of this paper is to reemphasize and analyze some necessary components of employee motivation, so contemporary managers; especially those who are inexperienced can enhance their knowledge and understanding of employee motivation. This paper explains the importance of employee motivation, describes the concept of motivation, and identifies

different motivators and priority changes in motivators over time. Some motivational programs and their examples are introduced and briefly described, and several theories and its organizational implications are identified and explained. This report suggests a sequential process of understanding employee motivation and that employee input must be valued and included in this process.

Past research showed that people are motivated by monetary rewards. However, on the contrary, high turnover in the oil and gas industry has reflected low commitment is still a major problem (MEF, Salary Survey for Executives/Non Executives 2010). This commitment issue has led the researcher to study that people may view monetary rewards as not ethical and may revert to motivational factors to make employee stay longer in an organization.

Motivation is one of the most important factors affecting human behaviour and performance. There were times when employees were considered to be another addition to enhance the production of services or goods. However, a lot has changed now. Elton Mayo conducted a research during the year 1924 and 1932 altered the way of thinking about employees.

This research was known as Hawthorne Studies. According to this study, employees require much more than just money. The study introduced the human relations approach to a company's management (Nickson, 1973). The main focus was given to the basic requirements and motivation factors of employees. The publication of the Hawthorne Study facilitated the understanding of factors that helped in motivating employees. There are several reasons that employees require to be motivated first, an organization

can easily survive when employees are motivated. Studies have proved that motivated employees are more productive. Managers must understand the factor that motivates employees with respect to the roles they perform. (Hedeian, 1993).

1.1 DEFINING MOTIVATION

Motivation is to inspire people to work, individually or in groups in the ways such as to produce best results. It is the will to act. It is the willingness to exert high levels of effort towards organizational goals, conditioned by the efforts and ability to satisfy some individual need (Kreitner, 1995).

Motivation is getting somebody to do something because they want to do it. It was once assumed that motivation had to be injected from outside, but it is now understood that everyone is motivated by several differing forces. (Buford et al., 1995).

Motivation is a general term applied to the entire class of drives, desires, needs, wishes and similar forces. To say that managers motivate their subordinates is to say that they do those things which they hope will satisfy these drives and desires and induce the subordinates to act in a desired manner (Higgins, 1994).

To motivate others is the most important of management tasks. It comprises the abilities to communicate, to set an example, to challenge, to encourage, to obtain feedback, to involve, to delegate, to develop and train, to inform, to brief and to provide a just reward. (Bedeian, 1993) For this paper, motivation is defined as the inner force that drives individuals to accomplish personal and organizational goals.

Motivation is the inner drive that pushes individuals to act or perform. Specific theories may propose varying set of factors influencing motivation (Harder, 2008) but many scholars agree that motivation is the psychological process that causes the arousal, direction, intensity and persistence of behavior (Locke and Latham, 2004; Pinder, 1998).

Fundamentally, motivation is the process that leads to behaviour, and this process cannot be directly measured or observed. Consequently, earlier researchers on motivation have identified various factors that could be applied in measuring motivation. In particular, Herzberg (1966) empirically identified satisfaction/no satisfaction factors and dissatisfaction/no-dissatisfaction factors as the determinants of staff motivation and staff contentment at work respectively. Satisfaction/no-satisfaction related factors motivate and/or de-motivate workers, while dissatisfaction/no-dissatisfaction factors provide hygienic and conducive working environment or non-hygienic and non-conducive working environment, which could either eliminate or encourage workers' complaints about working conditions. Jaafar, Ramayah and Zainal (2006) affirm that hygiene issues can minimize dissatisfaction if handled properly and can only dissatisfy if they are absent. Nelson and Quick (2003) note that motivation factors are the more important of the two sets of factors because they directly affect a person's motivation drive to do a good job. They added that hygienic factors only support the motivators but they (the hygienic factors) do not directly affect a person's motivation to work; they only influence the extent of the person's discontent.

Several models have been developed for measuring individual motivation. Herzberg Two-Factor theory was particularly developed to measure what motivates workers at work. Nelson and Quick (2003) contend that a

combination of motivation and hygiene factors could be used in measuring motivation and that a job high in motivation and hygiene factors leads to high motivation and few complaints among employees. For example, Gunu (2003) adopted the Herzberg's satisfaction/motivation model to determine job satisfaction among staff of public enterprises in Kwara State. In addition, Jaafar, Ramayah, and Zainal (2006) utilized Herzberg's satisfaction/motivation model to assess managers' job satisfaction in a construction company in Malaysia. Herzberg's hygiene and motivation factors was also applied to evaluate employees' job attraction and motivational factors in agro industry (see: Abdulsalam, Damisa, and Iliyasu, 2007). However, evidence of the application of Herzberg Two-Factor model to evaluate employees' performance in an academic setting is to the best of our knowledge, lacking. Hence, this study adopts same model (Herzberg's motivation model) to measure academic staff level of motivation at work. The study has gone a step further to adopt Herzberg's hygiene factor to assess academic staff level of dissatisfaction at work.

1.2 THE ROLE OF MOTIVATION

Why do we need motivated employees? The answer is survival (Smith, 1994). Motivated employees are needed in our rapidly changing workplaces. Motivated employees help organizations survive. Motivated employees are more productive. To be effective, managers need to understand what motivates employees within the context of the roles they perform. Of all the functions a manager performs, motivating employees is arguably the most complex. This is due, in part, to the fact that what motivates employees changes constantly (Bowen & Radhakrishna, 1991). For example, research suggests that as employees' income increases, money becomes less of a

motivator (Kovach, 1987). Also, as employees get older, interesting work becomes more of a motivator.

1.3 MOTIVATION THEORIES

In 1943 Abraham H. Maslow, the basis of Maslow's motivation theory is that human beings are motivated by unsatisfied needs, and that certain lower factors need to be satisfied before higher needs can be satisfied. According to Maslow, there are general types of needs (physiological, survival, safety, love, and esteem) that must be satisfied before a person can act unselfishly. He called these needs "deficiency needs." As long as we are motivated to satisfy these cravings, we are moving towards growth, toward self-actualization. Satisfying needs is healthy, while preventing gratification makes us sick or act evilly.

According to various literatures on motivation, individuals often have problems consistently articulating what they want from a job. Therefore, employers have ignored what individual's say that they want, instead telling employees what they want, based on what managers believe most people want under the circumstances. Frequently, these decisions have been based on Maslow's needs hierarchy, including the factor of prepotency. As a person advances through an organization, his employer supplies or provides opportunities to satisfy needs higher on Maslow's pyramid.

Frederick (1959) has tried to modify Maslow's need Hierarchy theory. His theory is also known as two-factor theory or Hygiene theory. He stated that there are certain satisfiers and dis satisfiers for employees at work. Intrinsic factors are related to job satisfaction, while extrinsic factors are associated with dissatisfaction. He devised his theory on the question: "What do people

want from their jobs?” He asked people to describe in detail, such situations when they felt exceptionally good or exceptionally bad. From the responses that he received, he concluded that opposite of satisfaction is not dissatisfaction. Removing dissatisfying characteristics from a job does not necessarily make the job satisfying. He states that presence of certain factors in the organization is natural and the presence of the same does not lead to motivation. However, their non-presence leads to demotivation. In similar manner there are certain factors, the absence of which causes no dissatisfaction, but their presence has motivational impact.

B.F. Skinner (1953), who propounded the reinforcement theory, holds that by designing the environment properly, individuals can be motivated. Instead of considering internal factors like impressions, feelings, attitudes and other cognitive behavior, individuals are directed by what happens in the environment external to them. Skinner states that work environment should be made suitable to the individuals and that punishment actually leads to frustration and de-motivation. Hence, the only way to motivate is to keep on making positive changes in the external environment of the organization.

The most widely accepted explanations of motivation have been propounded by Victor Vroom (1964). His theory is commonly known as expectancy theory. The theory argues that the strength of a tendency to act in a specific way depends on the strength of an expectation that the act will be followed by a given outcome and on the attractiveness of that outcome to the individual to make this simple, expectancy theory says that an employee can be motivated to perform better when there is a belief that the better performance will lead to good performance appraisal and that this shall

result into realization of personal goal in form of some reward. Therefore an employee is:

Motivation = Valence x Expectancy.

The theory focuses on three things:

- Efforts and performance relationship;
- Performance and reward relationship;
- Rewards and personal goal relationship.

The Adams' Equity (1965) Theory model extends beyond the individual self, and incorporates influence and comparison of other people's situations - for example colleagues and friends - in forming a comparative view and awareness of Equity, which commonly manifests as a sense of what is fair.

When people feel fairly or advantageously treated they are more likely to be motivated; when they feel unfairly treated they are highly prone to feelings of disaffection and demotivation. The way that people measure this sense of fairness is at the heart of Equity Theory.

Equity, and thereby the motivational situation we might seek to assess using the model, is not dependent on the extent to which a person believes reward exceeds effort, nor even necessarily on the belief that reward exceeds effort at all. Rather, Equity, and the sense of fairness which commonly underpins motivation, is dependent on the comparison a person makes between his or here reward/investment ratio with the ratio enjoyed (or suffered) by others considered to be in a similar situation.

1.4 EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION

The significance of employee motivation, influencing the behaviors of their employees to behave in certain ways, can ultimately decide the success or failure of an organization. Kovach (1987) suggests that if a company knows why its employees come to work on time, stay with the company for their full working lives, and are productive, then the company may be able to ensure that all of their employees behave in that way. Such a company would have a decided marketplace advantage over competitors suffering from absenteeism, costly re-training programs, and production slowdowns (p.58). Moreover, Wiley (1997) also suggests ensuring the success of a company, employers must understand what motivates their employees, and such understanding is essential to improving productivity (p. 271). These suggestions imply that organizational success depends heavily on employee motivation, and managers must understand what motivates their employees in order to motivate their employees. Understanding the concept of motivation could assist incompetent and inexperienced managers, in terms of employee motivation, identify what motivates their employees.

1.5. THE CONCEPT

What is motivation? Helliegele, Slocum, and Woodman (1992) describe motivation as the force acting on or within a person that causes the person to behave in a specific, goal-directed manner (p.204). Reece and Brandt (1990) suggest that motivation can be defined as the reason why people do the things they do, and in a work setting, motivation is what makes people want to work (p.149). Finally, Daft and Marcic (2004) explain that motivation refers to the forces either within or external to a person that arouse enthusiasm and persistence to pursue a certain course of action (p.444). These concepts of motivation suggest that motivation has something to do

with a person's behavior, a cause of behavior, or the reasons of individual behavior, and the causes of individual behaviors may differ because of different individual needs. The intuition of these concepts to managers is that they must first understand and discover these individual differences and their needs, and develop proper models to motivate employees by fulfilling these different needs toward common organizational objectives.

Therefore, organizations and managers should not limit themselves to one specific motivational factor; instead, they should consider diverse motivational models to realize the different needs of employees. Kovach (1987) supports this suggestion by saying that no standard motivational factor is applicable to all organizations because of individual differences. For example, what is interesting to one person may not be interesting to someone else: one employee may value good wage while the other may prefer interesting work (p.58).

A simple model of human motivation also concluded that a person's satisfaction can be received in the process of performing an action, intrinsic rewards, and others could receive their satisfaction from rewards given by the others, such as a promotion given by a manager, extrinsic rewards (Daft & Marcic, 2004, p.445). A variety of employee motivational factors have been identified and studied over the years and used by organizations to enhance managers' understanding of employee motivation. The research findings in the next section clearly indicate that employees are motivated by different reasons and their values change over time.

1.6 MOTIVATIONAL FACTORS

Wiley (1997) suggests that there are some motivators that employees value over time; however, the most preferred motivators have changed over the last 40 years. She refers to the survey results of 1946 by the Labor Relations Institutes of New York reported in *Foreman Facts*, similar surveys administered in 1980 and 1986 (Kovach, 1984 & 1987), and lastly her survey in 1992. Table 1 indicates ten motivators that employees were asked to rank. The top motivator selected by employees in 1946 was full appreciation of work done. Good wages ranked in the middle and interesting work ranked at number 7. In 1980 and 1986, employees' top concern was interesting work, followed by full appreciation of work done with good wages and job security near the middle. However, the respondents to the 1992 survey showed more concern for good wages followed by full appreciation of work and job security (pp.264-269).

Table 1. The "Factors That Motivate Me"

Motivators	1946	1980	1986	1992
Full appreciation of work done	1	2	2	2
Feeling of being in on thing	2	3	3	9
Sympathetic help with personal problems	3	9	10	10
Job security	4	4	4	3
Good wages	5	5	5	1
Interesting work	6	1	1	5
Promotion and growth in the organization	7	6	6	4
Personal loyalty to employees	8	8	8	6
Good working conditions	9	7	7	7
Tactful discipline	10	10	9	8

Note. From Wiley, C. (1997). What motivates employees according to over 40 years of motivation surveys. *International Journal of Manpower*, 18 (3), 263-281.

Table:1.51

These surveys proved that the priorities of employee motivational factors changed over time, and there is more than one reason why these changes occurred. The reasons may be economic conditions, change of working environment or industries, labor market conditions, industry competitions,

change in workers attitude, etc. For instance, Grayson and O'Dell (1988) explained that when World War II ended, U.S. productivity soared: benefiting from new technology, flexibility in labor force, and labor-management-government cooperation (p.61). Soared productivity and flexibility in labor force could have boosted an employment rate which in turn increased wage rates; therefore, employees were probably more concerned with intrinsic rewards during this period, such as full appreciation of work done, feeling of being in on things, and sympathetic help with personal problems. Furthermore, employees could have valued intrinsic rewards because having a job itself was satisfying their needs, a motivational factor, more than good wages or promotions due to the depression and war prior to this period.

In the 1980s, with almost forty years of relative prosperity and a rise in the standard of living beyond the imagination of workers in mid 40s, what workers wanted changed, however the findings of both 1980 and 1986 surveys supported that employees still valued intrinsic rewards, but not in terms of sympathetic help with personal problems. "Interesting work" was first, followed by full appreciation of work done and feeling of being in on things (Kovach, 1987, p.59). A national random sample of jobholders by the non-profit Public Agenda Foundation confirmed this indication. Its findings indicated that an impressive shift in attitudes towards work had developed, from work as a means of survival to work as a means of enhancing self-development and self-expression (Goddard 1989, p.7).

By the 1990s, it seems that workers valued more extrinsic rewards than intrinsic rewards. Good wage was chosen as the top motivator, full appreciation of work done next, followed by job security. Wiley (1997) reasoned that period-hostile takeovers, global competition, and

organizational transformation and downsizing created an environment that placed workers in a position of insecurity and uncertainty. Consequently, workers could have been more concerned with basic needs in this period: good wages and job security (p.23).

Increases in organizational downsizing, global competitions, and outsourcing have been described as general economic conditions for the last decade. Consequently, both organizational downsizing and outsourcing could have increased employees' workloads and feelings of job insecurity. These indications imply that current top motivators would still be job security and good wages. These motivational factors and changes in employee values due to different reasons can help current and future managers understand and discover the different needs of their workers, and make it easier for managers to choose and apply motivational programs that can be linked to the appropriate motivation theories.

Many programs have evolved for the purpose of attracting, maintaining, and motivating employees, and prior behavior in the evolution of these programs show that new programs will continue to be developed as work environments and employees' value change. Furthermore, a significant amount of theory building and research has focused on what energizes human behavior, and how certain behaviors can be sustained or maintained over time (Bowditch and Buono 1997, p.87). Furthermore, the major reason to study the theories of human behaviors is that good theory provides a basis for understanding, explaining, and predicting what will happen in the real world (Marrow 1965, p.7). Therefore, comprehending and knowing many theories may assist managers to design, develop, and implement appropriate motivational programs for their employees.

Programs, examples, and linked theories

For the purpose of this paper, this section will only identify and provide explanations of programs, theories, and examples from the work of Robbins (2005) to show managers how to identify, select, and link motivational programs to proper theories or vice versa. Table 2 shows that motivational programs are divided in two major categories, intrinsic and extrinsic rewards, and each reward is composed of three programs that are compatible with the concepts of each rewards. Additionally, some specific examples of each program are identified, and the relevant theories in the last column were included to link it to its pertinent programs. Managers should be aware that more than one theory can be identified with the appropriate programs, and understanding and studying of theories prior to learn particular programs can be sufficient enough as long as managers are be able to identify these theories to useful and related programs.

1.7 PROGRAMS AND EXAMPLES

In terms of intrinsic rewards, employee recognition programs focus on encouraging employees' specific types of behavior, so appropriate behaviors can be maintained and repeated. The examples of acknowledging and recognizing employees' desired behaviors are a simple thank you note, certificates of appreciation, or just saying "job well-done" or "thank you." Employee involvement programs are designed to increase employees' participation in the organizational decision-making process and their commitment to the organization's success. The first example of employee

Table 2. Types of Motivational Programs, Examples, and Linked Theories

Type of Rewards	Programs	Examples	Theories
Intrinsic (Self-satisfaction)	Employee Recognition	Thank you notes, Certificates of appreciation	Reinforcement Theory
	Employee Involvement	Participative management, Quality Circles, Employee Stock ownership	ERG Theory
	Job Redesign & Scheduling	Job sharing, rotation, enlargement, & enrichment, Flextime, Telecommuting	Two-Factor Theory
Extrinsic (Rewards given by others)	Variable Pay	Piece-rate pay plan, Gain sharing & Profit sharing plans, Bonuses	Expectancy Theory
	Skill-Based Pay	Skill, competence, knowledge based pay	ERG Theory
	Flexible Benefits	Modular plans, Core-plus plans, Flexible spending plans	Expectancy Theory

Note. From Robbins, S. P. (2005). Motivation: concepts to application. In C. University (Ed.), OM 8004: Managing and organizing people (pp.163-193). Boston: Pearson.

Table:1.61

involvement programs is participative management, which emphasizes joint decision-making. Representative participation is when elected or nominated employees represent themselves as all employees. Quality circles are generally composed of less than ten employees and supervisors who meet regularly to discuss quality programs. Employee stock ownership plans were created to increase employee commitment to accomplish organizational activities.

Finally, job redesign programs are focused on reshaping jobs in a way that employees do not feel boredom or repetition for a specific task. Examples of

these programs are job rotation, job enlargement, and job enrichment. Job scheduling programs are designed to allow employees some discretion over their work hours or schedules. For example, flextime allow employees to decide when to arrive and leave work, job sharing allows two or more individuals to split one permanent job, and telecommuting allows employees to perform their work from home at least two or three days a week.

The variable pay programs were the first programs identified in the extrinsic rewards segment, and it can be differentiated from the traditional compensation programs where an employee's pay is based on some organizational/individual measure of performance. The examples are a piece-rate plan based on each unit of production completed, a gain-sharing plan which is a formula-based group incentive plan, and profit-sharing plans are organization-wide programs that distribute the company's profit. Skill-based pay generally sets pay levels based on how many skills employees have or how many jobs they can do, also called competency-based or knowledge-based pay.

Flexible benefits allow employees to pick benefit packages that individually tailor to their own needs and situations. The most popular type of benefits are modular plans; pre-designed modules that meet needs of a specific group of employees. Next, core plus plans consist of a core of essential benefits plus other benefits that employees can add to the core, and flexible spending plans allow employees to set aside up to the dollar amount offered in the plan to pay for particular services (Robbins 2004, pp.165-187).

Linked theories

Robbins (2004) also linked employee recognition programs to reinforcement theory, and suggested that rewarding a behavior with recognition

immediately following that behavior is likely to encourage its repetition. He also indicated that employee involvement is compatible with ERG theory and efforts to stimulate the achievement need. He described that the enrichment of jobs can also be traced to Herzberg's two-factor theory by increasing the intrinsic factors in a job, such as achievement, responsibility, and growth, employees are more likely to be satisfied with the job and motivated to perform it.

With extrinsic rewards programs, he said, that variable pay is probably most compatible with expectancy theory because individuals perceive a strong relationship between their performance and rewards they receive if motivation is maximized. He also argued that organizational rewards should be linked to each individual employee's goals. Flexible benefits individualize rewards by allowing each employee to choose the compensation package that best satisfies his or her current needs. Finally, he said that skill-based pay plans are consistent with the ERG theory because it pays people to learn, expand their skills, and grow (pp.165-187). The above theories are linked to the programs examined and explained in the following.

Reinforcement Theory Reinforcement theory simply looks at the relationship between behavior and its consequences and focuses on changing or modifying the employees' on-the-job behavior through the appropriate use of immediate rewards and punishment. Behavior modification is the name given to a set of techniques by which reinforcement theory is used to modify human behavior. The basic assumption underlying behavior modification is the law of effect, which states that behavior that is positively reinforced tends to be repaired, and behavior that is not reinforced tends not to be repaired.

Reinforcement is defined as anything that causes a certain behavior to be repeated or inhibited. The first of four reinforcement tools is positive reinforcement, which suggests the administration of a pleasant and rewarding consequence following a desired behavior. For instance, immediate praise for an employee who arrives on time or does a little extra in their work will increase the likelihood of these desired behaviors occurring again. Next, avoid learning or negative reinforcement is the removal of an unpleasant consequence following a desired behavior where employees learn to do the right thing by avoiding unpleasant situations, and it occurs when a supervisor stops criticizing or reprimanding an employee once the incorrect behavior has stopped.

Thirdly, punishment is the imposition of unpleasant outcomes on an employee, and it occurs following undesirable behavior. Forms of punishment range from verbal reprimands to employee suspensions or firings. Finally, extinction is the withdrawal of a positive reward. Whereas with punishment, the supervisor imposes an unpleasant outcome such as a reprimand, extinction involves withholding pay raises, and other positive outcomes. The idea is that behavior that is not positively reinforced will occur less in the future (Daft & Marcic, 2004, p.459).

ERG Theory Wanous and Zwany (1977) suggests that Clay Alderfer's ERG theory holds that the individual has three sets of basic needs: existence, relatedness, and growth. Existence needs are satisfied by food, air, water, pay, fringe benefits, and work conditions. Relatedness needs are met by establishing and maintaining interpersonal relationships with coworkers, superiors, subordinates, friends, and family. Growth needs are expressed by an individual's attempt to find opportunities for unique personal development

by making creative or productive contribution at work. The major theme is that if a person is continually frustrated in attempts to satisfy growth needs, relatedness needs emerge as a major motivating force. The individual will return to satisfying this lower-level need instead of attempting to satisfy growth needs, and frustration will lead to regression.

This theory provides an important insight for team leaders. If a team leader sees that a subordinate's growth needs are blocked because the job does not permit satisfaction of these needs or there are no resources to satisfy them then the team leader should try to redirect the employee's behavior toward satisfying relatedness or existence needs (p.211).

Two-Factor Theory Fredrick Herzberg's two-factor or motivator hygiene theory is one of the most controversial theories of motivation probably because of its two unique features. First, the theory stresses that some job factors lead to satisfaction, where as the others can prevent dissatisfaction but do not serve as sources of satisfaction. Next, this theory states that job satisfaction and dissatisfaction do not exist on a single continuum. The motivator factors include the work itself, recognition, advancement, and responsibility. These factors are associated with an individual's positive feelings about the job and are related to the content of the job itself. These positive feelings, in turn, are associated with the individual's experiences of achievement, recognition, and responsibility, and they are predicated on lasting rather than temporary achievement in the work setting.

The hygiene factors, on the other hand, include company policy and administration, technical supervision, salary, working conditions, and interpersonal relations. These factors are associated with an individual's

negative feelings about the job and are related to the context or environment in which the job is performed, and these are extrinsic factors, or factors external to the job. In contrast, motivators are intrinsic factors or internal factors directly related to the job (Herzberg, Mausner, and Snyderman, 1959, p.216).

Expectancy Theory Expectancy theory suggests that motivation depends on individuals' expectations on their ability to perform tasks and receive desired rewards. This theory is based on the Employee Motivation: "Just Ask Your Employees" relationship between the individual's effort, individual's performance, and the desirability of outcomes associated with high performance. First relationship, effort and performance, involves whether putting effort into a task will lead to high performance. For this expectancy to be high, the individual must have the ability, previous experience, and necessary machinery, tools, and opportunity to perform.

The second relationship, performance and outcome, involves whether successful performance will lead to the desired outcome. For instance, an employee who is motivated to win a job-related award. This expectancy concerns the belief that high performance will truly lead to the award. However, if employees do not value the outcomes that are available from high effort and good performance, motivation will be low. Expectancy theory attempts not to define specific types of needs or rewards but only to establish that they exist and may be different for every individual. For example, one employee might want to be promoted to a position of increased responsibility, and another might have high valence for good relationships with peers. Therefore, the first person will be motivated to work hard for a promotion and the second for opportunity for a team position, that

will keep him or her associated with a group (Vroom, 1964, p.456). Once managers learn and understand a mixture of models and theories, they must evaluate and consider which programs are best suited for their organizations.

Increasing numbers of organizations are exploiting incentive plans as their motivational models today. For instance, a study titled “Managing Cash and Non-Cash Employee Rewards” recently released by the National Association for Employee Recognition (2005) indicates that half of all companies use cash awards to motivate employees, but there is no data to assess the appropriateness of this motivator (Incentive, p.1). Could incentive plans be the universal model? The next section will illustrate that managers have to understand that there are more programs than just incentive plans to motivate employees, but that is not to say that using incentive plans are inappropriate.

Incentive plans

The above information is in agreement with earlier assertion that the current top motivator for employees could very well be good wages. On the other hand, Kohn (1993) argues that most executives continue to rely on incentive programs because few people take the time to examine the connection between incentive programs and problems with workplace productivity and morale. Rewards are able to buy temporary compliance, so it seems as if problems are solved (pp.55-56). Furthermore, Kovach (1987) states that managers tend to ignore motivation theories, preferring to rely on their own preconceived notions of what turns their subordinates on, and the managers assume that what motivates them will also motivate those reporting to them.

Table 1.62 shows managers' perspectives on motivational factors over time, and all three surveys indicate that managers ranked good wages as top motivators: 1946, 1980, 1987, and these findings could have concluded that managers perceive that employees also are motivated by cash and incentive rewards. Nonetheless, if the findings of 1986 survey of supervisors are compared with the employee survey of Wiley (1992), managers' assumption could be justified. Bohlander and Snell (2004) state that there is a measurable relationship between incentive plans and improved organizational performance. In the area of manufacturing, productivity will often improve by as much as 20 percent after adoption of incentive plans, and service organizations, not-for-profits, and government agencies show productivity (p.427). If this is the result of incentive plans then some people could disagree with the arguments of Kohn (1993) and Kovach (1987), and fault their outdated data and findings from the surveys and studies. However, the following examples dispute the fact that incentive plans are major motivational programs, and these examples show that other programs could also produce the same or better results than incentive plans. eBay is growing at 72 percent a year, and Wall Street is wild about stock. One factor contributing to eBay's success is empowerment, the delegation of power and authority to the company's 2,400 employees . For example, CEO Meg Whitman, a one time Proctor & Gamble brand manager, Bain consultant, and Hasboro division manager, empowers her deputies to manage categories (toys, cars, collectibles) much as brand managers at P&G do Bounty or Tide. Highly motivated eBay employees have enabled the online auction site to attract 37 million customers with ever-increasing profits: \$129 million in a recent year (Daft and Marcic 2004, p.469).

Table 3. What People Want From Their Work (Ranked by the Supervisors)

Motivators	1946	1980	1986	Wiley's(1992) Survey (Employees)
Full appreciation of work done	8	8	8	2
Feeling of being in on thing	9	10	3	9
Sympathetic help with personal problems	10	9	10	10
Job security	2	2	2	3
Good wages	1	1	1	1
Interesting work	5	5	5	5
Promotion and growth in the organization	3	3	3	4
Personal loyalty to employees	6	7	7	6
Good working conditions	4	4	4	7
Tactful discipline	7	6	9	8

Note. From Wiley, C. (1997). What motivates employees according to over 40 years of motivation surveys. *International Journal of Manpower*, 18 (3), 263-281. Kovach, K. A. (1984). Why motivational theories don't work. *SAM Advanced Management Journal*, 45 (2), 54-60. Kovach, K. A. (1987). What motivates employees? Workers and supervisors give different answers. *Business Horizons*, 30 (5), 58-66.

Table 1.62

In addition, at Kraft Foods, employees at the company's Sussex, Wisconsin, food plant participated in work-redesign changes and team building that increased productivity, reduced overhead, and cut assembly time. Avon products empowered its minority managers to improve sales and service in inner-city markets. Grounded in the belief that minority managers had better understanding of the culture of inner-city residents, Avon turned an unprofitable market into a highly productive sales area (Bohlander and Snell 2004, p.109).

These examples are all successful cases of employee motivation with different models, and show that incentive plans may be the top motivator for both today's managers and employees, but not a universal model.

1.8 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study addresses the following objectives:

1. To determine the work motivation priorities of Central Office employees of Karnataka Milk federation, Bangalore.
2. To compare the difference in work motivation priorities between job types of Central Office employees of Karnataka Milk federation, Bangalore.
3. To describe the difference in work motivation priorities based on gender and ethnic background in Karnataka Milk federation, Bangalore.
4. To analyze and compare perceptions of supervisors and managers in regards to the work motivation preferences of the people they supervise.

1.9 NEED FOR THE STUDY

The researcher wishes to establish that there is a relationship between motivational factors, namely recognition, career development, work-life balance and benefits on employee commitment.

The need of this study will assist organizations in identifying and developing company's policies aimed at increasing employee commitment. To that effect, Human Resource Professionals can devise recognition initiatives, chart career developments plans, promote work-life balance programs and offer attractive benefits in increasing employee commitment.

The management can use the findings from this study to assist them to gain competitive advantage over their competitors in employee commitment from the same industry. This study is also aimed at helping employees to identify the motivational factors that will drive them towards being more committed and loyal to the organization. The employees will feel contented which is the factor that will make them stay longer in the organization. The longer employee stays with an organization, the more valuable they will be in terms of seniority, skill and knowledge.

With this study, the researcher also hopes to add value to body of knowledge to prove that motivational factors play eminent role in increasing employee commitment as mentioned in Maslow Revisited: Building the employee commitment pyramid (Stum, 2001).

1.10 RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

The research hypotheses for this study are:

H1: There is a relationship between recognition and employee commitment

H2: There is a relationship between career development and employee commitment

H3: There is a relationship between work-life balance and employee commitment

H4: There is a relationship between Incentive/benefits and employee commitment

H5: Motivational factors do have an impact on employee commitment

1.11 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. Time - limited time to collect back the questionnaires as some of the respondents may be working outstation or on a tour assignment.
2. Sample - select a sample population that may not reflect the overall population.
3. Respondents too dependent on the self-reported responses.

These abovementioned factors may affect the accuracy of the data and steps have been undertaken to reduce this problem by assuring the respondents that this study is confidential. Employees can then be rest assured as to provide true and fair opinion as they need not furnish their names in the questionnaire.

CHAPTER 2: REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A review of the literature indicates that there is a link between the industry that person is employed in and work motivation. Research also shows that work motivation will vary between industries and will also change over time.

Determining the reasons and factors why workers work has been the quest of industrial psychologists and management experts for years. It is generally agreed upon that if an employer can identify the reasons a worker is productive, reports to work on time, and remains with the company, the employer might then be able to apply these motivational factors unilaterally to the entire workforce. Applying this knowledge and fashioning the employment atmosphere to better accommodate the motivational factors of the employee, the employer becomes a more desirable employment destination, retaining employees longer, and increasing productivity and service at the same time.

2.1 THE CONCEPT OF MOTIVATION

Motivation, a Latin word “movere” means to move. Motivation is the activation or energization of goal-oriented behavior (Wikipedia, 2010). To Nelson and Quick (2003), motivation is the process of arousing and sustaining goal-directed behavior. Yet, Luthans (1998) sees it as the process that arouses, energizes, directs, and sustains behavior and performance, while Pinder (1998) defines work motivation as the set of internal and external forces that initiate work-related behavior, and determine its form, direction, intensity and duration.

The cited definitions shared some implicative commonalities. First, motivation is in-built in every human being and only needed to be activated or aroused. Second, motivation is temporal as a motivated person at one time can become de-motivated another time. Hence, individual motivation must be sustained and nourished after it has been effectively activated. Third, the essence of individual motivation in management or an organizational setting is to align employees behavior with that of the organization. That is, to direct the employees thinking and doing (performance) towards effective and efficient achievement of the organizational goals.

2.2 EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION

Employee motivation has been studied at length. Through research, a significant myth has been dispelled and shown to be incorrect. The biggest misconception was that good wages were always the primary motivational factor among employees regardless of the industry by which they are employed. This generalization, or supposed knowledge, has misdirected front line supervisors of industrial workers for years. The result has been misunderstood industrial employees who were more concerned with other motivational factors that their supervisors perceived as secondary or were not aware that existed. However, hospitality workers consistently rank good wages as their primary motivational factor. This is a good example of how motivation differs from one industry to another and why specific research is needed for each industry.

Review of the literature indicates identifying employee motivation is considered essential to understanding why an individual chooses one job

over another. Why does one employee work hard to complete a task and a co-worker feels no obligation to do the same; and, why does an employee continue to come to work when they have little or no desire to do the job? The questions of what motivates employees are of more importance today than ever before. Workforce moral is low due to downsizing and job instability, and there is no longer layers of management to supervise employees and keep them productive (McNerney 1996). Additionally, research indicates that productivity of employees decrease far more drastically after a co-worker quits for reasons of job satisfaction than when a co-worker quits because of illness (Sheehan 1993). There are a number of theories that have been developed by industrial psychologists and management experts that help to explain this dilemma.

It is time the human resource process of hiring, training, and retaining employees takes a step up to the next level. The paradigm has shifted and the hospitality and tourism industry, and the service industry must make the necessary accommodations to insure a high level of service to guests in order to remain competitive. There are new strategies to implement and the companies that reinvent the hiring process, providing superior customer service, are the organizations that will lead the service industry, but all of these strategies involve an increased understanding of employee behavior and their motivation.

2.3 JOB PERFORMANCE

Performance is behavior exhibited or something done by the employee (Campbell, 1990). According to Motowidlo, Borman and Schmidt (1997), job performance is the behavior that can be evaluated in terms of the extent to

which it contributes to organizational effectiveness (see: Onukwube, Iyabga and Fajana, 2010). Hillriegel, Jackson and Slocum (1999) see job performance as individual's work achievement after having exerted effort. Viswesveran and Ones (2000) regard it as the behavior and outcomes that employees engage in or bring about that are linked with and contribute to organizational goals (see: Onukwube et al., 2010). It is clear from these definitions that job performance is related to the extent to which an employee is able to accomplish the task assigned to him or her and how the accomplished task contributes to the realization of the organizational goal.

Job performance is not a single unified construct but a multidimensional construct consisting of more than one kind of behaviour. Onukwube et al. (2010) affirm that job performance was traditionally viewed as a single construct. However, Austin and Villanova (1992) and Campell (1990) argue that job performance is a complicated and multidimensional factor. Thus, Campbell (1990) proposed an eight-factor model of performance based on factor analytic research that attempts to capture dimensions of job performance existent (to a greater or lesser extent) across all jobs:

- i. Task specific behaviours which include those behaviours that an individual undertakes as part of a job. They are the core substantive tasks that delineate one job from another.
- ii. Non-task specific behaviour are those behaviours which an individual is required to undertake which do not pertain only to a particular job.
- iii. Written and oral communication tasks refer to activities where the incumbent is evaluated, not on the content of a message necessarily, but on the adeptness with which they deliver the communication.

Employees need to make formal and informal oral and written presentations to various audiences in many different jobs in the work force.

iv. An individual's performance can also be assessed in terms of effort, either day to day, when there are extraordinary circumstances. This factor reflects the degree to which people commit themselves to job tasks.

v. The performance domain might also include an aspect of personal discipline. Individuals would be expected to be in good standing with the law, not abuse alcohol, etc.

vi. In jobs where people work closely or are highly interdependent, performance may include the degree to which a person helps out the groups and his or her colleagues. This might include acting as a good role model, coaching, giving advice or helping maintain group goals.

vii. Many jobs also have supervisory or leadership component. The individual will be relied upon to undertake many of the things delineated under the previous factor and in addition will be responsible for meting out rewards and punishment. These aspects of performance happen in a face to face manner.

viii. Managerial and administrative performance entails those aspects of a job which serve the group or organization but do not involve direct supervision. A managerial task would be setting an organizational goal or responding to external stimuli to assist a group in achieving its goals. In addition, a manager might be responsible for monitoring organizational sources.

2.4 THEORIES OF MOTIVATION

There have been attempts to present models of motivation which list a specific number of motivating needs, with the implication that these list are all-inclusive and represent the total picture of needs. Unfortunately, each of

these models has weaknesses and gaps, and thus leaving the existing literature without a general theory of motivation.

The existing literature reveals several classifications of motivational theory. Motivational theories are generally classified into two (2): content motivation theories and process motivation theories (Anonymous, 2009). Content theories try to explain why people are motivated in different ways and in different work setting. In this category belongs 'need theories' (see: Maslow, 1954; Alderfer, 1972; and McClelland, 1965), job content theory (see: Herzberg, 1966; and Hackman and Oldham, 1975). The need theories maintain that an individual is motivated to do something if he or she experiences a specific need that may be fulfilled directly or indirectly by performing that action. However, the job content theories maintain that only aspects related to job content satisfy and motivate people to work. Specifically, Herzberg (1966) proposed a two factor (motivation-hygiene) motivation theory. The satisfier/motivators include achievement, recognition, work itself, responsibility, advancement and growth, while the hygiene factors include company policy and administration, supervision, relationship with supervisor, working conditions, personal life, salary, relationship with subordinates, status, and security. Motivators are the factors that fulfill individual's needs for meaning and personal growth; hygiene factors create dissatisfaction when they are mishandled. Cole (2005:98) states:

To take motoring analogy, hygiene factors can be considered as filling up the petrol tank, i.e. the car will not go, if there is no fuel, but refueling of itself does not get the vehicle under way. For forward

movement, the car electrics must be switched on and the starter operated – this is the effect created by the motivators.

Process or cognitive motivation theories attempt to understand how and why people are motivated. According to Cardona, Lawrence and Espejo (2003), cognitive development motivation tries to explain how people initiate, sustain, and terminate work motivation. Vroom's Expectancy Theory, Adam's Equity Theory, Locke's Goal Setting Theory and Skinner's Reinforcement Theory, etc. are example of process theories. Vroom's expectancy theory is founded on the basic notions that people desire certain outcomes of behavior and performance, which may be thought of as rewards or consequences of behavior, the performance they achieve, and the outcome they receive (Nelson and Quick, 2003). Equity theory suggest that individuals are motivated when they find themselves in situations of inequity or unfairness (Adams, 1963). Inequity occurs when a person receives more, or less, than the person believes is deserved based on effort and/or contribution. The goal setting theory assumes that human behavior is guided by conscious goal (see: Locke, 1968). Skinner's reinforcement theory hold that behavior can be controlled through the use of reward (see: Anonymous, 2002). Other motivation theories are intrinsic and extrinsic motivation theories, incentive theories, drive-reduction theories, broad theories, outcome theories, unconscious motivation theories, etc.

2.5 PREVIOUS RESEARCH ON LEVEL OF STAFF MOTIVATION, JOB DISSATISFACTION AND JOB PERFORMANCE IN THE PRIVATE AND PUBLIC SECTORS

Previous studies on the level of staff motivation and job performance in the profit and non-profit organizations have yielded differing results. A study by

Eze (1995) revealed that there is significant difference between the high-order motivators and the lower-order motivators and that being preoccupied with the motivators in one set would inhibit the urge to satisfy the motivators in the other set. The lower-order motivators (e.g. human physiological needs such as needs for food, clean water, clothing, shelter, and sex/marriage) are basic to Nigerian workers and more proponent than the higher order motives (Eze, 1995). Employees of the Kwara State Government, Nigeria were dissatisfied with their physiological needs (e.g. salary) (see: Gunu, 2003). Thus, Karwai (2005) argues that as long the human basic needs (or lower-order motivators) remain the major problem of workers in Nigeria, the quest for money which is the ultimate means of acquiring goods and service through whatever means (e.g. corruption, fraud, thuggery, militancy, robbery) will remain the order of the day and as such, a serious societal problem.

Gunu (2003) established employees' satisfaction with their esteem needs (e.g. promotion), and safety needs (e.g. work itself). High level of staff motivation and job satisfaction was found to exist among the employees of an agribusiness in Zarai, Nigeria (see: Abdulsalam, Damisa and Iliyasu, 2007). Isaac (2008) observed poor attitude to work among civil servants of Akwa Ibon State, Nigeria, which instigated him to probe into causes of such behavior. His study revealed low motivation among the staff, and high absenteeism from work, low punctuality to work, indolent to work, and fraudulent behavior. Furthermore, a significant relationship was established between motivation and employees' punctuality to work, motivation and indolent behavior, motivation and attitude to work, motivation and fraudulent behavior, and motivation and absenteeism (Isaac, 2008). Abejirinde (2009) used two motivational indicators, namely growth and promotion, to determine the level of staff motivation in the Nigerian public and private sectors. He

established high rate of growth and promotion opportunities for the employees in both private and public organization. He equally established high rate of job performance among the staff.

Maslow's Need Hierarchy Theory

One of the better known theories of motivation is Maslow's Need Hierarchy Theory. Maslow (1943) proposed that all individuals have a basic set of needs that need to be fulfilled over the course of a lifetime. This is a broad theory on human development and its application is generally considered to be the adult years, thus the industrial application is that people strive to meet their needs in a work environment. Maslow arranged the needs in a hierarchical order and proposed that individuals have five basic sets of needs; Physiological needs, Safety needs, Love needs, Esteem needs, and Self-actualization needs. The need that is unsatisfied at any given time is the need considered to be the most important. Initially the research on Maslow's theory was cross-sectional by design, but recently longitudinal studies have been used to support the cross-sectional studies. If Maslow's theory has value in relationship to work motivation, it is in these longitudinal studies that examine the changing priorities of the needs as other needs reach an acceptable level of satisfaction (Landry 1985). Work motivational factors change over a period of time.

Herzberg

The concept of separating motivational factors was brought forward by Herzberg (1968). Herzberg advocates separating the hygiene factors with their negative connotation from the positive factors considered inherent to the job: recognition, achievement, responsibility, and growth or

advancement. The intent is to focus on the higher level needs rather than the negative result and use this as a basis for job enrichment and motivation.

Herzberg's Two Factor Theory is a "content theory" of motivation" (the other main one is Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs).

Herzberg analysed the job attitudes of 200 accountants and engineers who were asked to recall when they had felt positive or negative at work and the reasons why.

From this research, Herzberg suggested a two-step approach to understanding employee motivation and satisfaction:

Figure No:2.51

Hygiene Factors

Hygiene factors are based on the need to for a business to avoid unpleasantness at work. If these factors are considered inadequate by employees, then they can cause dissatisfaction with work. Hygiene factors include:

- ✓ Company policy and administration
- ✓ Wages, salaries and other financial remuneration
- ✓ Quality of supervision

- ✓ Quality of inter-personal relations
- ✓ Working conditions
- ✓ Feelings of job security

Motivator Factors

Motivator factors are based on an individual's need for personal growth. When they exist, motivator factors actively create job satisfaction. If they are effective, then they can motivate an individual to achieve above-average performance and effort. Motivator factors include:

- ✓ Status
- ✓ Opportunity for advancement
- ✓ Gaining recognition
- ✓ Responsibility
- ✓ Challenging / stimulating work
- ✓ Sense of personal achievement & personal growth in a job

There is some similarity between Herzberg's and Maslow's models. They both suggest that needs have to be satisfied for the employee to be motivated. However, Herzberg argues that only the higher levels of the Maslow Hierarchy (e.g. self-actualisation, esteem needs) act as a motivator. The remaining needs can only cause dissatisfaction if not addressed.

Applying Hertzberg's model to de-motivated workers

What might the evidence of de-motivated employees be in a business?

- Low productivity
- Poor production or service quality
- Strikes / industrial disputes / breakdowns in employee communication and relationships

- Complaints about pay and working conditions

According to Herzberg, management should focus on rearranging work so that motivator factors can take effect. He suggested three ways in which this could be done:

⇒ Job enlargement

⇒ Job rotation

⇒ Job enrichment

Industrial Employees

Dr. Kenneth Kovach is a professor of management at George Mason University at Fairfax, Virginia. Kovach (1987) has surveyed industrial employees over a period of forty years. This questionnaire focuses on the positive, higher level motivational needs and was applied prior to Herzberg's documentation. In 1946 Kovach surveyed industrial employees and asked them to rank ten job reward factors in terms of personal preference.

The results were as follows:

1. Full appreciation of work done;
2. Feeling of being in on things;
3. Sympathetic help with personal problems;
4. Job security;
5. Good wages;
6. Interesting work;
7. Promotion and growth in the organization;
8. Personal Loyalty to employees;
9. Good working conditions
10. Tactful discipline;

A similar questionnaire was given to industrial employees in 1981, and again in 1986. By 1981 “interesting work” was the top motivating factor and “sympathetic help with personal problems” had fallen from third on the list to ninth. The 1986 questionnaire also had significant changes with “sympathetic help” falling to number ten and only “job security” and “personal loyalty” remaining in their original positions from the 1946 survey. The one consistent response from all three surveys was that supervisors perceived “good wage” as the top motivational factor for the employees they supervise. Supervisors and managers seem to operate from a self-reference point of view. They seem to think that their employees want the same things that they do and fail to take into account individual needs.

Kovach also hypothesized that the work motivational factors may be different between categories of employees based on sex, age, income, job type and organizational level. The 1986 questionnaire was broken into subgroups to allow for this hypothesis to be tested. There were only minor differences between the gender responses; however, there were significant differences between age groups and the findings were that “good wage” was the top ranked job reward of the younger employees and it descended in rank as the age group matured. The questionnaire also showed significant differences between traditional blue collar and white-collar jobs. The blue-collar worker was more concerned with “appreciation for work done” while the focus of the white-collar worker was “interesting work”. Management needs to understand employees within the context of the job they perform to properly understand what their needs are.

Hospitality Industry

There have been a number of applications of Kovach's questionnaire in the hospitality industry where traditional hospitality jobs in the private sector differ significantly from industrial jobs. The questionnaire has been applied utilizing methods in the Casino industry (Darder 1994). Casino dealers show results similar to the industrial workers in that their work motivational priorities changed over a period of time. The dealers were surveyed in 1946, 1980, 1986, and 1987, however the dealer's priorities of work motivational factors differed from the industrial worker. The dealers responses remained relatively consistent over the first three applications but significant changes were seen in the 1987 responses. "Interesting work" fell from the top spot and "full appreciation for a job well done" replaced it in the top motivational slot. Also moving up in motivational priority was "good wages," "promotion and growth," and "sympathetic help with personal problems."

The questionnaire was also used on hotel workers in the United States and the results were directly compared to industrial workers (Simons, Enz, 1995). The hotel works ranked "good wages," "job security," and "opportunity for advancement" as their top three work motivational factors. These hospitality employees employed in the private sector differed somewhat from their counter parts in the industrial labor field as they ranked "interesting work," "appreciation for a job well done," and "feeling of being in on things" as their top three work motivational factors. These differences could be attributed to the nature of the hospitality industry where guest appreciation can account for the decreased need for appreciation from supervisors and the raised need of communication to accommodate the ever-changing need of individual hotel guests. The responses were also broken down by sub-

categories and there was a significant variance about the job level with the skilled or semi-skilled laborers more interested in “job opportunities” and the unskilled labor force more focused on “job security.” There was no significant variance in the gender responses.

The questionnaire has also been applied in the Caribbean to hotel workers (Charles, Marshall 1992). The findings of the survey were similar to other private hotel employees in several respects but the Caribbean hotel worker ranked “good working conditions,” “appreciation for a job well done,” and “interesting work” higher than the United States hotel workers. It is important to note that both groups are employed in the hospitality industry, but the variance in responses can be attributed to the separate cultures. Flores (1989) states that successful North American hospitality service managers in Puerto Rico are the managers that have taken the time to understand the culture and social environment. Puerto Ricans are warm friendly people who value smiles and small talk from supervisors and managers that can be overlooked or forgotten in the work-place in the United States. This is a good example of why people need to be managed as individuals and not lumped into groups. Cultural diversity exists in all facets of the workforce, but is especially prevalent among the unskilled labor force.

A more recent application of Kovach’s motivational scale was in Hong Kong (Tsang, Wong, 1997). The scale was applied to Hong Kong’s hotel employees. The survey concluded that the number one motivational factor of Hong Kong hotel employees was opportunities for advancement and the number two motivational factor was loyalty to employees. The results of the Hong Kong survey differed from the American hotel worker survey completed

in 1995. The Hong Kong hotel worker is focused more on long-term objectives where the American hotel worker seems focused on the short-term with good wage being the number one motivational factor. The variance between the two surveys can be attributed to cultural differences. Further analysis found that motivational preferences of the Hong Kong hotel worker did in fact vary based on the hotel department where they were employed.

Employment Forecast

Low unemployment in the United States is forecasted to continue for some time. The majority of industries across the United States are facing a labor shortage. (Caudron, 1996). This shortage is felt in both blue and white-collar industries. Companies that were downsizing a few years ago are finding it difficult to find staff to expand. The end result is that companies now have to recruit as they never had before. The hospitality and convention industry is not immune to the labor shortage. The high percentage of unskilled labor jobs in the industry has employers vying for available workers. Additionally, these same employers are now considering people candidates that they would not have considered five years ago, and looking at alternative means of retention that was not considered reasonable five years ago.

Employee loyalty is on the decline (Stum, 1998). Employee loyalty can be considered a causality of the transformation from the industrial age to the informational age. However, the employees are not entirely to blame for the demise. Organizational change is responsible for the elimination of the old social contract and as a result a new, a more independent workforce has emerged. Research has helped to determine what this new work force is looking for. Today's employee is more educated, wary, and diverse than

ever before. They possess an entrepreneurial quality that has them balancing the work-life equation in an effort to reduce work related stress and focus on the other portions of their life. Work is no longer considered the driving force of today's employee. The end result is fewer full-time employees and more part-time and alternative staff.

Strum (1998) identifies five commitment drivers for employees. The number one employment factor, or driver, employees are looking for is a fearless culture. Employees value a nontraditional approach where traditional ways and procedures are questioned. This requires open, honest, and at times, a confrontational approach to communication. The second driver is job satisfaction. Hiring the right person for the right job has long had a strong correlation to performance and commitment. Opportunities for personal growth is the third driver. Today's worker is looking to grow and expand their knowledge and responsibilities; however, personal growth can be found through nontraditional means like job sharing or conferences, not just expanded responsibilities. Organization direction is the fourth employee driver. Faith that the organization is solvent and doing well is important to retention. This faith allows the employee to commit fully to the organization with the confidence that the organization will be present for years to come. Gone are the days when an individual commits to an organization with the idea that the relationship will be long-term and that the organization will act as the custodian of the retirement benefits. The final driver is the employer's ability to recognize the need for work-life balance. This understanding and promotion of well-rounded people helps the employee identify with the organization and distinguish a correlation, or like mindedness between the employee and the organization. This appears to be a by-product of the X

Generation where people of this generation feel less of a need to live by the nine to five rules of the Baby Boomer Generation.

Age has an impact on work motivation, and the X Generation is a good example. Values most important for the X Generation are a sense of belonging/teamwork, the ability to learn new things, entrepreneurship, flexibility, security, and short term rewards. (Jurkiewicz, 2000). This generation is perceived as being more skeptical than the Boomers of traditional relationships in the workplace that are hierarchical, and believe that a manager needs to earn respect rather than deserve respect.

Traditional marketing techniques have been employed to attract customers to hospitality and tourism companies for years. These same techniques must now be applied to the workforce to attract employees. (Taylor, Cosenza, 1997). The goal of an internal marketing strategy is to develop consistency in employee programs and increase customer satisfaction among the employee/customer attracting employees of all generations. Organizations have their own culture. The culture must be communicated and reinforced so that it can be a positive motivational influence on the employees and promote involvement and interaction. The employee employer relationship must change to meet these new demands. Employers now must focus on relationships and communication with the employee in order to better meet their needs. Employers no longer can take employees for granted and treating your employees as well as your customers appears to be the new standard for success. Empowerment is another key to increased retention, provide employees with the tools necessary to do the job and let be your customer service representative.

Hiring

One key factor to retaining more employees is doing a better job of hiring an employee in the first place. The rush for employers to hire new staff has compounded the retention issue. The fundamentals of good hiring practices are more important than ever, however the time consuming basics like background checks, references, and even the interview process, are being altered in an effort to get new employees faster. Employers must be as diligent as ever in assessing candidates so those new employees are a good fit for the organization. One strategy is to hold interviews at different hours to see how an employee might perform at the time they would normally work. This would be especially effective for an employee who works late or is required to arrive early in the morning. (Hertneky, 1999).

Training has long been a human resources buzzword. Training programs can have a significant impact on employee retention. Employees who receive extensive training generally feel rewarded and realize the investment and commitment that their employer is making. However, one size fits all training no longer provides an employer with an edge. It is not unusual for an employee to embrace one portion of their employment more than another. This is an opportunity to apply a technique called job sculpting. Job sculpting is nothing more than identifying the life interests of an employee, or, what makes them happy (Butler, 1999). This alignment of interests and tasks has proven useful to employees who have established themselves with an organization. Often times the alteration of tasks is minimal and may require added responsibilities to enable the employee to pursue these interests. Job sculpting also has an application as a recruitment tool to attract new employees to an organization, but it is the development of the relationship

between the manager and the employee that enables job sculpting to be successful. A relationship that is based on trust is the core of job sculpting. Employers who take the time to develop a relationship out of concern and caring are the employers who will have a higher retention rate because they will be able to motivate their employees.

Demotivators

Every bit as important as identifying what an employee wants is knowing what employees don't want. Avoiding demotivators is another key to staff retention. Different aspects of the job will attract different employees, but demotivators will be around long after an employee has chosen a job. (Spitzer, 1995) These obstacles to blissful employment can take on a number of forms. Politics and unclear expectations are two problems that organizations face. Other problems that have a negative effect are constant change, low quality standards, and unproductive meetings. The first step to eliminating these moral busters is to obtain employee feedback to identify consistent themes. Employees tend to appreciate these collaborative efforts as they are viewed as tangible efforts to improve the quality of the work environment. Employers who assume that they know what the problems are relying on their own perspective and fail to see the issue through the eyes of their employees.

Benefits

Dutton (1998) provides good examples of emerging trends in the field of employee benefits aimed at retaining staff. Dutton clearly states that the most important benefits are the health and pension benefits. This is a well-established truth, however the benefit industry has gone to the next level to

distinguish benefits within employment opportunities. The term used to identify this new type of employee benefit is “Soft Benefits”. These soft benefits are considered secondary benefits, something to be considered when all else is equal. These benefits can provide for a wide variety of compensation and protect employees in different areas. Good examples of soft benefits might include onsite flu shots, take-home meals, or even onsite physical or massage therapy. The primary idea behind soft benefits is that the benefits will allow the employee more time to focus at work. The above examples have been utilized at the Cigna Corporation in Philadelphia. Other examples of soft benefits are lactation programs and facilities for nursing mothers, adoption benefits, and legal assistance benefits.

The West Group in Eagan, Minnesota now provides a variety of services at the employment site in an effort to simplify their employees lives. West has developed a storefront complex that they call Main Street that includes dry cleaning service, a floral shop, credit union, as well a convenience store (Dutton,1998).

The concept of soft benefits is a solid one. If an employee’s life can be simplified they in theory have more time to dedicate to work. Many of the benefits listed are routine errands that people have to accomplish on a daily basis. Employers can take it a step father, and already do. Many of these soft benefits are more informational by nature. While this type of benefit can cost money from a research and development standpoint, that can be the majority of the expense, as much of the benefit is informational or subcontracted to local vendors.

Review of the literature has indicated that employee retention is a significant issue in the hospitality and tourism industry. Additionally, the literature indicates that there are a number of other factors that can affect the motivational needs of employees in both industries. Age, sex, income and job level are all factors to be considered, as is the cultural environment. Identifying employee motivation is a key to employee retention. Employers who understand the needs of their employees have a better opportunity to fulfill these needs and retain productive employees for a longer period of time.

Azoulay, Graff-Zivin, Manso (2010), professors at Massachusetts Institute of Technology and University of California, Santa Barbara, published a paper titled "Incentives and Creativity: Evidence from the Academic Life Sciences" indicating that long term rewards rather than short term rewards helped to motivate scientists in their work and to promote overall greater creativity. The application of this study suggests that short term rewards, that are common in many businesses, may truncate motivation and hinder innovation.

For example, some people enjoy immediate satisfaction and some enjoy satisfaction that is delayed but has taken time to build up. Recognition is a key role in motivating which is a non-financial incentive that reflects feedback.

Schimdt, Boraie and Kassabgy (1996) used the dichotomy of extrinsic and intrinsic motivation for their questionnaire. A questionnaire for motivational factors includes 50 items: Intrinsic motivation, 5 items; extrinsic motivation, 15 items; personal goals, 5 items, expectancy/control components, 9 items;

attitudes, 4 items; anxiety, 6 items; and motivational strengths, 6 items. The factor analysis produced nine factors: determination, anxiety, instrumental motivation, sociability, attitudes to culture, foreign residence, intrinsic motivation, beliefs about failure, and enjoyment. Schmidt et al. defined extrinsic motivation as motivation to obtain an external reward and intrinsic motivation as motivation to get sufficient rewards from the activity itself. They stated that intrinsic-extrinsic distinction is similar to integrative-instrumental distinction, but not identical. Both instrumental and integrative motivation can be seen as subtypes of extrinsic motivation, because both are related to goals and outcome.

Jacques (2001) developed a questionnaire based on Schmidt et al. 1996. There are three types of student questionnaires. One of them includes 52 items concerning motivation: integrative orientation, interest in foreign language and cultures, language requirement, heritage requirement, instrumental orientation, intrinsic motivation, etc. After factor analysis, six factors were extracted: value components, expectancy components, motivational strength, competitiveness, heritage languages and cooperativeness.

Noels, Clement and Pelletier (1999) investigated how students' perceptions of their teachers' communicative style, particularly the extent to which teachers are perceived to support student's autonomy and to provide useful feedback about students' learning progress, are related to students' extrinsic and intrinsic motivational orientations. The study also examined the link between these variables and various language learning outcomes, including effort, anxiety, and language competence. Students registered in a summer

French immersion program (N=78) completed a questionnaire that was used to assess the constructs described above. Correlational analyses determined that stronger feelings of intrinsic motivation were related to positive language learning outcomes, including greater motivational intensity, greater self-evaluations of competence, and a reduction in anxiety. Moreover, perceptions of the teacher's communicative style were related to intrinsic motivation, such that the more controlling and the less informative students perceived the teacher to be the lowest students' intrinsic motivation was. The implications of perceptions of teacher communicative style for motivation and language learning outcomes are discussed.

By and large, these studies on motivation have presented pertinent discussions as to the importance of motivation in language learning. It has been shown that teachers are influential in their students' motivation towards their own learning competencies. Although some studies also presented that students do not need to be motivated to learn certain skills. Another study presented additional variables not found in the existing standardized questionnaires on motivation, as other interesting indicators may stimulate learner's motivation to learn pertinent skills. And finally, an investigation of how intrinsic motivation influence positive learning outcomes of the learners has given an added dimension to the growing number of studies done on motivation.

The purpose of research conducted by James Lindner (1998) Research and Extension Associate at The Ohio State University Piketon Research and Extension Center was to describe the importance of certain factors in motivating employees at the Piketon Research and Extension Center and

Enterprise Center. Specifically, the study sought to determine the ranked importance of ten motivating factors. The final ranked order of these factors was:

- Interesting work
- Good wages
- Full appreciation of work done
- Job security
- Good working conditions
- Promotions and growth in the organization
- Feelings of being in on things
- Personal loyalty to employees
- Tactful discipline
- Sympathetic help with personal problems

Two further studies cited by Lindner returned the following results:

A study of industrial employees conducted by Kovach (1987) yielded the following ranked order of motivational factors (a) interesting work, (b) full appreciation of work done and (c) a feeling of being in on things.

The second study, also on employees and conducted by Harpaz (1990) found the following rankings of motivational factors:

- ✓ interesting work
- ✓ good wages
- ✓ job security

The final conclusions that Lindner draws from his own and others research is that ""The discrepancies in these research findings supports the idea that what motivates employees differs given the context in which the employee

works. What is clear, however, is that employees rank interesting work as the most important motivational factor".

A study of employee attitudes undertaken by the Gallup Organisation with more than 100,00 employees in 12 industries using 12 statements, shows employees who have a positive attitude toward their work are 50% more likely to achieve customer loyalty and 44% more likely to produce above-average profitability. Companies whose support of the 12 statements ranked in the top 25% averaged 24% higher profitability, 29% higher revenues and 10% lower employee turnover. The statements included:

- I know what is expected of me at work
- At work, I have the opportunity to do what I do best every day
- In the past seven days I have received recognition or praise for doing good work
- My supervisor, or someone at work, seems to care about me as a person
- There is someone at work who encourages my development
- A study by John Throop (cited in IOMA's Pay for Performance Report 1998) conducted using computer programmers, asked participants to identify the top 10 factors that provided the highest degree of motivation in their jobs. The programmers top three were:
 - Full appreciation for work done
 - Feeling that they were in on things
 - Sympathetic help with personnel problems

When asked what the top motivators would be, the managers of these programmers predicted rather different priorities with the three top ranking items being:

- ✓ Wages
- ✓ Working conditions
- ✓ Fair discipline

CHAPTER 3: COMPANY PROFILE

Karnataka Cooperative Milk Producers' Federation Limited (KMF) is the Apex Body in Karnataka representing Dairy Farmers' Co-operatives. It is the second largest dairy co-operative amongst the dairy cooperatives in the country. In South India it stands first in terms of procurement as well as sales. One of the core functions of the Federation is marketing of Milk and Milk Products. The Brand "**nandini**" is the household name for Pure and Fresh milk and milk products.

KMF has 13 Milk Unions throughout the State which procure milk from Primary Dairy Cooperative Societies(DCS) and distribute milk to the consumers in various Towns/Cities/Rural markets in Karnataka.

The first ever World Bank funded Dairy Development Program in the country started in Karnataka with the organisation of Village Level Dairy Co-operatives in 1974. The AMUL pattern of dairy co-operatives started functioning in Karnataka from 1974-75 with the financial assistance from World Bank, Operation Flood II & III. The dairy co-operatives were established under the ANAND pattern in a three tier structure with the Village Level Dairy Co-operatives forming the base level, the District Level Milk Unions at the middle level to take care of the procurement, processing and

marketing of milk and the Karnataka Milk Federation as the Apex Body to coordinate the growth of the sector at the State level.

Coordination of activities among the Unions and developing market for Milk and Milk products is the responsibility of KMF. Marketing Milk in the respective jurisdiction is organized by the respective Milk Unions. Surplus/deficit of liquid milk among the member Milk Unions is monitored by the Federation. While the marketing of all the Milk Products is organized by KMF, both within and outside the State, all the Milk and Milk products are sold under a common brand name NANDINI.

KARNATAKA MILK FEDERATION LTD

The Karnataka Cooperative Milk Producers Federation Ltd., a cooperative apex body in Karnataka, has been implementing Dairy Development activities in the entire State since 3 and half decades in a phased manner through the 13 district milk unions, ushering prosperity in the lives of rural Milk Producers.

3.1 :BACKGROUND

- The first ever World Bank funded Dairy Development integrated project was launched in 1975 on cooperative principles covering 8 southern districts initially and KDDC was setup for implementation.

Figure 3.11 Karnataka cattles

- KMF came into existence in 1984 and Dairy Development activities were extended to cover the entire state under Operation Flood-II.
- OF-II ended in 1987 and the process of Dairy Development continued through 13 District Milk Unions under OF-III from 1987 to 1996.

- The post operation Flood and Perspective Plan works are carried out from 1996 in coordination with NDDB.

3.2 OBJECTIVES

- To build primary Dairy Co-operative Societies in cooperative sector to manage the dairy activities
- Providing assured and remunerative market for the milk produced by the farmer members

VILLAGE LEVEL DAIRY Figure 3.21 →

- Providing quality milk & milk products to urban consumers.
- To ensure provision of milk production inputs, processing facilities and dissemination of knowhow.
- To facilitate rural development by providing opportunities for self employment at village level, preventing migration to urban areas, introducing cash economy and opportunity for steady income.

3.3 AFFILIATED MILK UNIONS AT DISTRICT LEVEL

The Federation in its fold has 13 District Milk Unions spread-over the entire State of Karnataka covering all 30 Districts by cooperative dairying activity.

The District Milk Unions in operation are Bangalore, Kolar, Mysore, Mandya, Tumkur, Hassan, Dharwad, Belgaum, Bijapur, Gulbarga, D.Kananda , Shimoga and Bellary.

The coverage of Districts by Unions is as below.

- 3 Unions - 1 district each
- 4 Unions - 2 districts each
- 5 Unions - 3 districts each
- 1 Union - 4 districts

MEGA DAIRY, BANGALORE Figure 3.31

3.4 KMF ORGANIZATION CHART

The organization is three tiered on Co-operative principles.

- A. Dairy Co-operative Societies at grass root Village level.
- B. District Co-operative Milk Unions at single / multi district level.
- C. Milk Federation at State level.

FIGURE 3.41 :- 3 TIER SYSTEM OF KMF

All above three are governed by democratically elected board from among the milk producers. Under the direction of elected boards, KMF, various functional Units & Unions are performing the assigned tasks to ensure fulfilment of organisation objectives.

3.5. Board of Directors-KMF

SRI G.SOMASEKHARA REDDY
CHAIRMAN

H.D.REVANNA
HASSAN UNION

G.P.REVANASIDDAPPA
SHIMOGA UNION

H.J.CHANDRU
MANDYA UNION

K.V.NAGARAJU
KOLAR- CHIKKABALLAPURA UNION

H.K.RENUKA PRASAD
TUMKUR UNION

P.NAGARAJU
BANGALORE UNION

SANJAY GOWDA R PATIL
BELGAUM UNION

MARUTHI KASHAMPURA
GULBARGA-BIDAR UNION

MALLIKARJUNA SHANKARAPPA JAGURA
BIJAPUR-BAGALKOTE UNION

RAVIRAJ HEGDE
DK-MANGALORE UNION

S KRISHNAPPA(EX MLA)
NOMINATED DIRECTOR

JAYAKUMARA KANGE
NOMINATED DIRECTOR

PRAMILA MALLIKARJUN
NOMINATED DIRECTOR

S.C.ASHOK
MYSORE-CHAMARAJANAGAR UNION

ARAVIND JANNU, IAS
PRINCIPAL SECRETARY TO GOK AH&F

DR.D.M.DAS
DIRECTOR AH&VS DEP, GOK

S.G.HEGDE, IAS
RCS, GOK

B S KHANNA
GM, NDDB

A S PREMANATH
MANAGING DIRECTOR, KMF

3.6 Human Resource Development

There are at present 20.35 Lakh dairy farmers as primary members including 3.5 Lakhs of SC/ST and 6.6 Lakh woman members.

Dairy Co-operatives employ more than 32000 people and 5200 are permanent KMF Units and Unions employees.

Indirect employment thro' veterinary services, milk transportation, milk sales etc. activities is to the tune of 52000 people.

This sector has also created demand and employment in manufacturers of equipments required by DCS, Dairies, printing and the like.

3.7 THE GROWTH PROCESS

The growth over the years and activities undertaken by KMF is summarized briefly hereunder:

3.71 PERSPECTIVE PLAN 2010

After the closure of OF-III project. Government of Karnataka and NDDB signed an MOU during February 2000, for further strengthening the Dairy Development Activities in Karnataka with an outlay of Rs.250 Crores. Consequent to the announcement of new lending terms and conditions by NDDB through an evolution of an action plan - Perspective 2010 to enable the dairy cooperatives to face the challenges of the increased demand for milk and milk products by focusing efforts in the four major thrust areas of Strengthening the Cooperatives. Enhancing Productivity, Managing Quality and building a National Information Network, plans are under implementation.

3.72. FUTURE VISION

To consolidate the gains of Dairying achieved in the state of Karnataka and with a view to efficiently chill, process and market ever developing and increasing milk procurement with an utmost emphasis on the Quality and in the process conserve the socio-economic interests of rural milk producers, the Govt. of Karnataka through KMF has proposed to undertake several projects with financial and technical support of NDDB for which an MOU was signed between Govt. of Karnataka and NDDB on 10th Nov. 2004.

3.73 .Other GOK Financial Support:

1. To support Milk Producers of DCS members GOK is providing an amount of Rs.2.00 per litre as incentive to the milk producer from 2008-09 onwards.
2. GOK is providing financial assistance for strengthening Dairy Development infrastructure facilities at Northern Karnataka milk unions jurisdiction which will also redress regional imbalance as per Dr. Nanjundappa's report.

3.8UNITS OF KMF

The Following KMF Units are in operation to cater to the needs of centralized Technical Input facilities.

Figure :3.81. :-Mother Dairy, Yelahanka, Bangalore
(including Ice Cream plant, Powder plant)

Dairy Processes around 7 LLPD by receiving milk only in Tankers and selling more than 3.10 LLPD. It has Ice cream plant of 10000 LPD & 30 MTD capacity Powder Plant.

Figure 3,82 :-Nandini Milk Products, KMF Complex, Bangalore.

The unit has specialized production of milk based ethnic sweets like Mysore Pak, Peda , Khova, Besan laddoo,Burfi, Nandini Bite, Jamoon etc. which have great festive demand.

Figure:3.83:- Cattle Feed Plant, Rajanukunte,Gubbi,Dharwad and Hassan.

- The combined Production capacity of all 4 plants is 1000MT with capacity Utilization of more than 115%.
- All 4 Plants are ISO 9001:2000certified.
- Three varieties of Feed along with Urea Molasses Brick at

Rajankunte & Mineral Mixture in Gubbi & Hassan Plant are produced

Figure 3.84:- Nandini Sperm Station, Hessarghatta:
The unit is engaged in Production & supply of around 2.40 million doses annually of superior quality Semen to all DCS through milk unions. This unit is graded as 'A' grade station by GOI.

Figure 3.85"- Nandini Packaging Film Plant, Munnekolalu:
To meet milk Unions pouch film demand, the plant with capacity of 2700 MTs capacity / annum is working with maximum capacity utilization

Figure 3.86:- Training Institutes:
The Central Training Institute at B'lore and Training centres at Mysore & Dharwad are imparting need based training programs to DCS Staff, DCS members & Officers/ Staff of KMF, Unions & Units.

Figure 3.87:- Nandini Hi-Tech Product Plant:
This unit was set up in 2005 to handle the surplus milk of Mysore, Tumkur, Hassan and Mandya Milk Unions with product dairy of 400 TLPD and 30 MTPD powder plant. In 2011 UHT Milk

Processing and packing is also Facilitated with the processing capacity of 1,00,000 Ltrs/ Day .

3.9: Vision

- To march forward with a missionary zeal which will make KMF a trailblazer of exemplary performance and achievements beckoning other Milk Federations in the country in pursuit of total emulation of its good deeds.
- To ensure prosperity of the rural Milk producers who are ultimate owners of the Federation.

- To promote producer oriented viable cooperative society to impart an impetus to the rural income, dairy productivity and rural employment.
- To abridge the gap between price of milk procurement and sale price.
- To develop business acumen in marketing and trading disciplines so as to serve consumers with quality milk, give a fillip to the income of milk producers.
- To compete with MNCs and Private Dairies with better quality of milk and milk products and in the process sustain invincibility of cooperatives.

3.10:MISSION

Heralding economic, social and cultural prosperity in the lives of our milk producer members by promoting vibrant, self-sustaining and holistic cooperative dairy development in Karnataka State

3.11:Objectives

KMF is a Cooperative Apex Body in the State of Karnataka representing organisations of milk producers' and implementing around dairy development activities to achieve the following objectives:

- To ensure assured and remunerative market round the year for the milk produced by the farmer members.
- To make available quality milk and other premier dairy products to urban consumers.
- To build & develop village level institutions as cooperative model units to manage the dairy activities.
- To ensure provision of inputs for milk production, processing facilities and dissemination of know how.

- To facilitate rural development by providing opportunities for self employment at village level, preventing migration to urban areas, introducing cash economy and opportunity for a sustained income.

The philosophy of dairy development is to eliminate middlemen and organise institutions to be owned and managed by the milk producers themselves, employing professionals. To sum it up, every activity of KMF revolves around meeting one basic objective: 'Achieve economies of scale to ensure maximum returns to the milk producers, at the same time facilitate wholesome milk at reasonable price to urban consumers'. Ultimately, the complex network of cooperative organisation should build a bridge between masses of rural producers and millions of urban consumers and in the process achieve a socio-economic revolution in every hinterland of the State.

3.12:Evolution

Karnataka Milk Federation which is most popular as KMF, evolved itself as a premier and most profitable dairy farmers' organization in the State of Karnataka.

As an agency in 1975 to implement the World Bank Aided Dairy Development Projects, Karnataka Dairy Development Corporation (KDDC) was formed, the company grew itself fast and as it spreads the wings of new found rural economic activity - Dairying all over the State, the genesis of apex cooperative body took the shape of KMF in 1983 encompassing entire State with 13 District Co-operative Milk Unions executing the various parameters of Dairy activity - organization of Dairy Co-operatives, Milk Routes, Veterinary Services, Procurement of milk in two shifts of the day,

Chilling, Processing of milk, distribution of milk and also establishment of Cattle Feed Plants, Nandini Sperm Station, Liquid Nitrogen Supply, Training Centres - as its main stay.

The entire system was reconstructed on the model of now well known 'ANAND' pattern dairy cooperative societies. Eight southern districts of Karnataka was considered initially with a target of organizing 1800 Dairy Co-operative Societies, four Milk Unions and processing facilities were set up to the tune of 6.5 lakhs per day by 1984.

Under Operation Flood - II & III, project which started in 1984 & 1987 covered the remaining parts of Karnataka. Thirteen milk unions are organized in 175 talukas of all 20 districts then and the field work was extended by organizing more dairy cooperative societies. The processing facilities i.e. chilling centers, milk dairies and powder plants were transferred in phases to the administrative control of respective cooperative milk unions and the activities continued to be implemented by these District Organisations. Additional processing facilities were created & existing facilities augmented every decade with the help of Govt. / Zilla Panchayat and NDDB to handle ever increasing milk procurement without declaring milk holidays. The processing facility as exists at 32.25 lakh liters/day is further strengthened.

3.13:KMF PHYSICAL ACHIEVEMENTS:

Figure 3.131

By FEB 2013, a network of **13,553 Dairy Cooperative Societies (DCS)** have been organized, in 13 milk Unions. Among them 12035 DCS are functioning with 96% of them

are in profit. About 2906 women DCS are functioning.]

These DCS are spread over 170 talukas covering 21,593 villages, in all the 30 Districts of Karnataka.

About 22.16 lakhs rural farmers are members in these DCS, of which 8.20 lakhs are Small Farmers, 6.43 lakhs are Marginal Farmers, 3.96 lakhs landless labourers and 3.57 lakhs are Others. Out of these 2.30 & 1.26 lakhs of them belong to SC & ST groups and 7.49 lakhs are Women Members.

← **Fig 3.132- MILK PROCUREMENT GROWTH**

The DCS carries out milk procurement activity on all the 365 days procuring an avg. proc. of 49.25 lakhs kgs per day in 2012-13 in the State.

The highest procurement was 54.55 lakh kgs/day recorded in NOV '2012.

The surplus milk is handled, without resorting to milk procurement holidays.

Karnataka Milk Federation Ltd stands in 2nd position in milk procurement at the National level and 1st Position in South India.

There are 22 dairies, with a total processing capacity of 40.10 lakh ltrs. Per day, 47 milk chilling centers with chilling capacity 19.55 lakh.ltrs per day and 5 milk powder plants with drying capacity of 100 MT per day. An average 29.96 lakh.ltrs per day is sold as fluid milk, out of which, an avg. of 16.20 Lakh. Ltrs is sold in Bangalore City.

Figure3.133
MILK SALES GROTH ↓

3.14 :MARKETING IN KMF

Wide range of milk and value-added milk products were sold under the brand name of **Nandini** and have made Nandini the most-trusted dairy brand for customers. Umbrella branding is the key factor for Nandini's

Figure 3.141 NEW PRODUCT LAUNCH

Today, Nandini markets a range of 58 milk and Milk products in 203 different stock keeping units(SKU) offering customers with plentiful of choices

- ✚ Fresh products like Toned, HCM, DTM, FCM, Shubam, Curds, Butter Milk & Lassi.
- ✚ Frozen products like Ice cream, Frozen Desert in different flavors.
- ✚ Ethnic Indian sweets prepared from pure milk/ghee like Mysore Pak, Burfi, Pedra, Besan laddoo, Khova Jamoon, Dry Fruit Burfi, Rasagulla, Jamoon Mix, Nandini Bite & Sugar free pedra
- ✚ Fat based products like Ghee, Butter, Paneer, Yogurt, Cheese and Khova
- ✚ Powder based products like dairy whitener and SMP
- ✚ Goodlife Milk in different variants (Slim, Smart, Super, Sampoorna) in addition to new Generation drinks in new tetra pack variants of Flavoured Milk/ Butter Milk by adopting UHT TREATMENT TECHNOLOGY.

The brand positioned as the No. 1 milk brand in southern India and No. 2 milk brand in India among cooperatives.

Figure 3.142- Registered LOGO of “nandini” brand

Nandini has won “The Most Valuable Brand in Karnataka Award” in The Sunday Indian & IIPM Regional Excellence Awards 2009.

Over the years, Nandini’s product basket is steadily growing. Consumer demands are increasing, choices are widening. Competitors are multiplying in the market day-by-day to fulfill consumer demands and sustain market leadership, new products in stunning packages are launched periodically.

Figure 3.143

Nandini basket of milk and milk products

Buy the best quality
beyond compare

Pasteurised Double Toned Milk Pasteurised Toned Milk Homogenised Pasteurised Cow Milk Shubham Pasteurised Standardised Milk GoodLife Milk in Tetra Pak Brik & Fino Packages

GoodLife Slim Milk in Tetra Pak Brik & Fino Packages Smart Double Toned Milk in Tetra Pak Brik & Fino Package Samporna Standardised Milk in Tetra Pak Brik Package Curd Real Thick Curd Butter Milk

Sweet Lassi Flavoured Milk - Badam, Pista, Strawberry & Choco Milk Shake in Tetrapak Slim Package Spiced Butter Milk in Tetrapak Slim Package Flavoured Milk - Badam, Pista, Banana & Elaichi in Bottle Badam Powder in Container & Sachet

Skimmed Milk Powder Dairy Whitener Paneer Khova Butter - Salted Ghee in Sachet, Bag-in-box, Standy-pouch, Pet Jar & Tin

Vermicelli Payasa (Kheer) Cheddar Cheese Processed Cheese Block Processed Cheese Spread (Plain) Processed Cheese Spread (Capsicum) Processed Cheese Spread (Pepper) Gulab Jamoon Mix Kunda

Mysore Pak Cashew Burfi Badam Burfi Besan Ladoo Pure Milk Peda Dharwad Peda

Sugar Free Peda Dry Fruits Burfi Chocolate Burfi Coconut Burfi Ready to eat Khova Jamoon Rossogolla

Family Pack Ice Creams - Aniir, Black Currant, Kaju Draksh, Butter Scotch, Chocolate, Kesar Pista, Mango, Pineapple, Strawberry, Vanilla Cup Ice Creams - Butter Scotch, Chocolate, Kesar Pista.

3.15:KMF DEPOTS IN OPERATION

To cater to the increasing demand & sales of milk and milk products region wise depots have been commissioned.

- ◆ Bangalore Sales Depot
Covering Urban & Rural Bangalore, Ramanagara, Mandya, Mysore, Chamarajanagara, Kolar, Chikkaballapur, Tumkur, Hassan, Chikkamagalore & Chitradurga.

FIGURE 3.151 →

- ◆ Mangalore Sales Depot-Covering Udupi, Dakshina Kannada.
- ◆ Tirupati Sales Depot Covering Andhra Pradesh State.

FIGURE 3.152
OPENING OF A NEW DEPOT ↓

- ◆ Kannur Sales Depot-Covering Kerala State.
- ◆ Hubli Sales Depot
Covering Shimoga, Dharwad, Gadaga, Belgaum, Bagalkote, Uttar Kannada, Bellary & Koppal.
- ◆ Gulbarga Sales Depot
Covering Gulbarga, Raichur, Bidar & Bijapur.
- ◆ Mysore Sales Depot
Covering Mysore & Chamarajanagara.
- ◆ Bellary Sales Depot

FIGURE 3.153:DEPOWISE WSDs AND RETAILERS

3.16 :THE FINANCIAL PROGRESS

The Federation has maintained low price spread between procurement and sale price which has resulted in higher realization. In FEB.'13, on an average 8.5 Crores(Approx) is being paid per day to the milk producers.

FIGURE 3.161 →

AWARDING “KSHEERA BHANDU” TITLE TO KARNATAKA CHIEF MINISTER

The overall impetus given by the Federation to the Dairy development activities in the State has resulted in higher procurement of milk, which is handled without declaring any milk holiday.

← FIGURE 3.162
KMF TURN OVER

The adequate processing facilities coupled with new marketing strategies resulted in higher turnover. There is a marked increase of 5800.00 Crores(Approx) in 2011-12 as compared to 950.00 Crores(Approx) in the year 1999-2000 with a growth of 483%.

3.17:PERFORMANCE HIGHLIGHTS

- 96% of the Milk Producers Cooperative Societies are earning profit.
- Low price spread between procurement and sale prices resulted in payment of higher price to producers. An Average of Rs.21.50 per Kg. of milk for 3.5% fat and 8.5% SNF is paid to DCS.
- A latest state-of-the-art technology Mega Dairy with a processing capacity of 6 LLPD expandable up to 10 LLPD has been commissioned in Bangalore.
- An Ice Cream Plant at the cost of 3 crores with capacity of 3000 LPD was established in 1997 & later expanded to 10000 LPD Capacity (Rs.369 Lakhs) in 2005.
- To facilitate conversion of surplus milk into milk powder, a milk powder plant at Mother Dairy at a cost of Rs.22 Crores has been established during October 2002
- To facilitate the manufacture of Export-Oriented Milk Product,a new State-of-art Product Plant is Commissioned at Channarayapatna in Hassan district at a cost of Rs. 72 crore to handle surplus milk of Mysore, Tumkur, Hassan and Mandya Milk Unions.
- Chilling Centre of 1 LLPD expandable up to 1.5 LLPD at 450 Lakhs has also been commissioned at Channarayapatna.
- The diversification in the year 2000 into UHT(Ultra High Temperature) treatment process has seen the launch of “Good Life” pure cow milk with a shelf life of 60 days without refrigeration in different variants(Good life,

FIGURE 3.131 ↓

Slim, Smart & Sampurna). Infrastructure facility has been expanded to 1.8 LLPD from 40 LPD at Kolar Milk Union.

FIGURE 3.172 →

- Strengthening/Expansion of Mother Dairy, Bangalore adopting modern technology from 4 LLPD to 7 LLPD of milk handling facilities at an outlay of Rs.35 Crores in 2010
- A New Hi-Tech 300MTs balanced Cattlefeed Plant to meet burgeoning demand for balanced Cattlefeed in the state is commissioned at Hassan during Jan.2012 with an outlay of 39 crores.
- Expansion of Dharwad Cattle Feed Plants capacity from 150 MTD to 200 MTD and establishing mineral mixture production unit.
- The four Cattle Feed Plants owned by KMF have been awarded with the ISO 9001:2000 certificate for best-maintained quality standards. Due to increased demand, the combined capacity utilization of the Plants has far exceeded 140%.
- B'lore has obtained ISO 22000:2005, which is the first Dairy in south India to get the Certification, Kolar, Mother Dairy have also obtained this certification.
- Dakshina Kannada, Mysore, Kolar & Tumkur Unions have obtained ISO 9001-2000, HACCP & GMP certificates. Hassan & Shimoga Unions have also obtained ISO 9001-2000.
- About 13108 MTs of Nandini Ghee has been supplied during 2001-2012 to Thirumala Thirupathi Devasthanam.
- Opening of "Nandini Dairy Farmers Welfare Trust" Hostel for farmers children at the cost of 12.96 Crores for higher education of 600 boys and 400 Girls.
- Successfully implementing Central Govt schemes such as Clean Milk Production Programme, Special Package for Suicide Prone Districts Fodder Development etc., & State Govt scheme such as "Amrutha Yojana",

Redressal of Regional imbalances, Special Component Plan and Tribal Subplan.

- Other Schemes being implemented are Grants/relief, Grants for Gulbarga/Bidar Union, Establishment of Chilling Centers at Gulbarga and Belgaum Division.
- Modernization of mineral mixture plant to produce high quality mineral mixture in association with research & development wing of NDDB at all Cattle Feed Plants .
- Establishment of UHT (Tetrapack) Plant at Channarayapatna Product Plant of 1 lakh Lpd capacity is commissioned.

3.18:ON-GOING PROJECTS

- Establishing a CFP 300 MT at Shikaripur in Shimoga Dist at the cost of Rs 40 Crores.
- Establishing Fodder Densification Units of 12 Mt capacity at the cost of Rs.2.12 crores (grant) at Chamarajanagara commissioned is in progress, and Haveri nearing completion.
- Construction of 5000 Mt storage capacity godowns at Dharwad Cattle Feed Plant and 2500 Mt capacity at Gubbi Cattle Feed Plant to facilitate storage of raw material at the plants.
- Construction of 10 lakh ltr capacity Tetra Pack Milk storage godown at Channarayapatna.
- Establishing a new 10000 Ltr Capacity Ice cream Plant at Bellary at the cost of 10Crores.
- Commissioning of 1 lakh LLPD Tetra Pack unit @ Mandya @ the cost of Rs.9 crores is in progress.
- Expansion of Nandini Milk Products at the cost of Rs 2 Crores.
- Strengthening of Training centers at the cost of 3 crores under RKVY scheme.
- Ksheerabhavan construction at the cost of Rs. 7 Crores is in final stage at Channapatna village, Hassan District

3.19:ON-GOING PROGRAMS

- Continue to implement and improve the Total Energy Management and Clean Milk Production programme with added vigour.

- To implement STEP Programme under Department of Women and Children Welfare, Human Resources Department, Government of India.
- Adoption of Progeny Testing Scheme (PTS) under NDP for improved productivity of milk through milk recording and nominated service to produce Bull Calves for the future need of the Federation.

3.20 :DEVELOPMENT PROJECTS

- Dairy of capacity 3 LLPD at Kolar Union (Cost- Rs. 50 to 60 crores.)
- Chilling center of capacity 1 LLPD at Arasikere of Hassan Union (Rs. 10 crores).
- Modern mega Cattlefeed Plant of 500MTs capacity in the outskirts of Bangalore (channapatna) (Rs. 82 crores).
- Commissioning of Nandini Cross-breed heifers project (Nandini Cow/Buffaloe heifers Bank) at Hesarghatta (Rs. 40 to 50 crores.)
- Expansion of Nandini Packaging Film Plant at Munekollal (Rs 25 crores.)
- Flexi Pack Unit at Belgaum (Rs 10 crores.)

CHAPTER 4: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

One of the vital keys to any research work is the research and analysis of its steps that are implemented. These steps must be appropriate to test hypotheses or questions of the research and also to facilitate the accessibility of overall design of the research such as collection of data and analysis of data. This chapter describes the approaches that are used in this study in order to test the hypotheses of the problem under the study and provides the reader with a basis for evaluating the validity of findings, an understanding of the basis for choices that were made and sufficient details that another researcher can replicate this study. In this chapter, some vital objects related to research methodology such as problem under the study,

initial literature review, objectives and hypotheses and their methodologies developed for them, data instruments including collection of data and analysis of data are in details explained and finally at the end of this chapter the limitations and conclusion of research methodology are stated.

The system of collecting data for research projects is known as research methodology. The data may be collected for either theoretical or practical research for example management research may be strategically conceptualized along with operational planning methods and change management.

Some important factors in research methodology include validity of research data, Ethics and the reliability of measures most of your work is finished by the time you finish the analysis of your data.

Formulating of research questions along with sampling whether probable or non probable is followed by measurement that includes surveys and scaling. This is followed by research design, which may be either experimental or quasi-experimental. The last two stages are data analysis and finally writing the research paper, which is organized carefully into graphs and tables so that only important relevant data is shown.

4.1.RESEARCH DEFINITION

Kothari (2004) defines that the research is an original contribution to the existing stock of knowledge making for its development. The systematic approach concerning generalisations and formulation of a theory is also

research. As such the term 'research' refers to the systematic method consisting of enunciating the problem, formulating a hypothesis, collecting the data, analysing the facts and reaching certain conclusions either in the form of solutions(s) towards the concerned problem or in certain generation for some theoretical formulation. According to Greenfield (1996), Research is an art aided by skills of inquiry, experimental design, data collection, measurement and analysis, by interpretation, and by presentation. A further skill, which can be acquired and developed, is creativity or invention.

Also Noltingk (1965) believes that Research is in essence an investigation into processes. Therefore a research is the finding of answers related to the questions. It is a systematic search for truth, finding new knowledge about our world through combination of ideas and facts.

The research was done at Karnataka Milk Federation Ltd, Bangalore.

4.2 Research design

The research design is descriptive design.

4.3.Data source

Primary Data- The primary data was collected from the Central office employees of KMF by administering a structured questionnaire.

Secondary Data- Apart from primary data collected, the data collected from the web and literature

4.4.Sampling unit

Central Office , Karnataka Milk Federation Ltd, Bangalore.

4.5.Sampling size

100 Employees

4.6.Sampling type

A total number of 100 employees were selected randomly from different cadre and from departments of Central office complex of Karnataka Milk Federation Ltd, situated in Bangalore. So the sampling type is simple random sampling.

4.7.Plan of data analysis

Diagrams, graphs, pie charts, will be used for data analysis.

CHAPTER 5.0: DATA ANALYSIS, RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

1. Age Group

TABLE 5.1

Age Group	
1	Under 30
2	30-39
3	40-49
4	50&above

Age Group	
Under 30	10%
30-39	65%
40-49	23%
50& above	2%

FIGURE 5.1

Interpretation

Most of the respondent (i.e 65%) are between the age group of 30-39 years while only 2% of the respondent are above the group of 50 years and above. 10% of the respondents are under the age group of 30 years while 23% of the respondents are between the age group of 40-49 years.

2. Highest Qualification

1	Highest Qualification
2	Below Graduation
3	Graduation
4	Post Graduation

TABLE 5.2

Highest Qualification	
Below Graduation	20%
Graduation	65%
Post Graduation	15%

FIGURE 5.2

Interpretation

65% of the respondents are completed graduation while 20% of the respondents are below graduates. However, only 15% of the respondents are Post graduates.

3. Length of service

TABLE 5.3

1	Length of service
2	Above 20 Years
3	15-20 years
4	10-15 years
5	Less than 10 years

Length of service	
Above 20 Years	56%
15-20Years	24%
10-15 years	12%
Less than 10 years	8%

FIGURE 5.3

Interpretation

56% of the respondents working in the organization are above 20 years while 24% of the respondents are working in the organization between 15-20 years. 12% of the respondents are working in the organization between 10-15 years while 8% of the respondents are working in the organization for less than 10 years.

4. Are you satisfied with the support from the HR department?

1. Highly satisfied
2. Satisfied
3. Neutral
4. Dissatisfied
5. Highly Dissatisfied

TABLE 5.4

Are you satisfied with the support from HR department	
Highly Satisfied	5%
Satisfied	35%
Neutral	44%
Dissatisfied	12%
Highly Dissatisfied	4%

FIGURE 5.4

Interpretation

5% of the respondents are highly satisfied with the support from HR department while 4% of the respondents are highly dissatisfied. 44% of the respondents are neutral while 12% of the respondents are dissatisfied with the support from HR department and 35% are satisfied

5. Management is really interested in motivating the employees?

1. Strongly agree
2. Agree
3. Neutral
4. Disagree
5. Strongly disagree

TABLE 5.5

Management is really interested in Motivating the employees	
Strongly agree	2%
Agree	10%
Neutral	25%
Disagree	46%
Strongly disagree	17%

FIGURE 5.5

Interpretation

46% of the respondents disagree that the management is really interested in motivating the employees while 10% of the respondents agree with this statement. 25% of the respondents are neutral while 17% of the respondents strongly disagree that the management is really interested in motivating the employees while only 2% of the respondents strongly agree to this statement.

6. Which type of incentives motivates you more?

1. Financial incentives
2. Non-financial incentives
3. Both

TABLE 5.6

Which types of incentives motivates you more?	
Financial incentives	68%
Non-Financial incentives	24%
Both	8%

FIGURE 5.6

Interpretation

68% of the respondents believe that only financial incentives motivates them while 24% of the respondents are in favor of Non-financial incentives. However, only 8% of the respondents believe that both types of incentives motivates them.

7. How far you are satisfied with the incentives provided by the organization?

1. Highly satisfied
2. Satisfied
3. Neutral
4. Dissatisfied
5. Highly Dissatisfied

TABLE 5.7

How far are you satisfied with the incentives provided by the organisation	
Highly satisfied	3%
Satisfied	19%
Neutral	25%
Dissatisfied	35%
Highly dissatisfied	18%

FIGURE 5.7

Interpretation

3% of the respondents are highly satisfied with the incentives provided by the organization while 18% of the respondents are highly dissatisfied with the incentives scheme of the organization. 19% of the respondents are satisfied while 35% of the respondents dislike the incentive scheme provided by the organization. 25% of the respondents are neutral.

8. You get reasonable periodical increase in salary

1. Strongly agree
2. Agree
3. Neutral
4. Disagree
5. Strongly disagree

TABLE: 5.8

You get reasonable periodical increase in salary	
Strongly agree	2%
Agree	25%
Neutral	15%
Disagree	48%
Strongly disagree	10%

FIGURE 5.8

Interpretation

2% of the respondents strongly agree with the reasonable periodical increase in salary by organization while 10% of the respondents strongly disagree with this statement. 25% of the respondents agree that the organization provide reasonable periodical salary increase while 48% of the respondents disagree with this statement. 15% of the respondents are neutral to this statement.

9. Job security exist in the company

1. Strongly agree
2. Agree
3. Neutral
4. Disagree
5. Strongly disagree

TABLE 5.9

Job security exist in the company	
Strongly agree	40%
Agree	30%
Neutral	17%
Disagree	12%
Strongly disagree	1%

FIGURE 5.9

Interpretation

30% of the respondents agree that the job security exist in the company while 1% of the respondents strongly disagree with this statement. 17% of the respondents are neutral. 12% of the respondents disagree that the job security exist in the company while majority of the respondents (i.e 40%) strongly agree that the job security exist in the organization.

10. Good relationship with co-workers exists in the organisation

1. Strongly agree

TABLE 5.10

2. Agree

3. Neutral

4. Disagree

5. Strongly disagree

Good relationship with co-workers exist in the organisation	
Strongly agree	20%
Agree	45%
Neutral	5%
Disagree	19%
Strongly disagree	11%

FIGURE 5.10

Interpretation

20% of the respondents strongly agree that good relationship with co-workers exist in the organization while 11% of the respondents strongly disagree with this statement. Majority of the respondents (i.e 45%) only agree that good relationship with co-workers exist in the organization while 19% of the respondents disagree with this statement. 5% of the respondents are neutral.

11. Organization has the effective performance appraisal system

TABLE:5.11

1. Strongly agree
2. Agree
3. Neutral
4. Disagree
5. Strongly disagree

Organisation has the effective performance appraisal system	
Strongly agree	3%
Agree	10%
Neutral	10%
Disagree	59%
Strongly disagree	18%

FIGURE 5.11

Interpretation

Majority of the respondents (i.e 59%) disagree that the organization has the effective performance appraisal system while 10% of the respondents agree with this statement. 10% of the respondents are neutral and they neither agree nor disagree with the statement. However, there are only 3% of the respondents who strongly agree that the organization has the effective performance appraisal system while 18% of the respondents strongly disagree with this statement.

12. Do you have the opportunity to further develop your skills and abilities?

- 1. Yes
- 2. No

TABLE 5.12

Do you have the opportunity to develop your skills and abilities	
Yes	38%
No	62%

FIGURE 5.12

Interpretation

62% of the respondents believe that they do not have the opportunity to develop their skills and abilities while 38% of the respondents think that they have the opportunity to develop their skills and abilities.

13. Organization has the effective promotional opportunities

1. Strongly agree

TABLE 5.13

2. Agree

3. Neutral

4. Disagree

5. Strongly disagree

Organisation has effective promotional opportunities	
Strongly agree	15%
Agree	46%
Neutral	5%
Disagree	28%
Strongly disagree	6%

FIGURE 5.13

Interpretation

15% of the respondents strongly agree that the organization has effective promotional opportunities while 6% of the respondents strongly disagree with this statement. However, there are 46% of the respondents who only agree with this statement while 28% of the respondents only disagree with this statement. There are 5% of the respondents who neither agree nor disagree that the organization has effective promotional opportunities

14. Good safety measures are adopted in the organization

1. Strongly agree

TABLE 5.14

2. Agree

3. Neutral

4. Disagree

5. Strongly disagree

Good safety measures are adopted in the organisation	
Strongly agree	19%
Agree	36%
Neutral	3%
Disagree	30%
Strongly disagree	12%

FIGURE 5.14

Interpretation

19% of the respondents strongly agree whereas only 12% of the respondents strongly disagree that the safety measures adopted by the organization are good. 3% of the respondents are neutral. Majority of the respondents (i.e 36%) agree with this statement while 30% of the respondents disagree that good safety measures are adopted in the organization.

15. Performance appraisal activities are helpful to get motivated.

1. Strongly agree
2. Agree
3. Neutral
4. Disagree
5. Strongly disagree

TABLE 5.15

Performance appraisal activities are helpful to get motivated	
Strongly agree	9%
Agree	19%
Neutral	5%
Disagree	65%
Strongly disagree	2%

FIGURE 5.15

Interpretation

65% of the respondents disagree that the performance appraisal activities of the organization are helpful to get motivated while 19% of the respondents agree with this statement. However, there are 9% of the respondents who strongly agree that the performance appraisal activities of the organization are helpful to get motivated while 2% of the respondents strongly disagree with this statement. 5% of the respondents are neutral.

16. Support from the co-worker is helpful to get motivated

1. Strongly agree

TABLE 5.16

2. Agree

3. Neutral

4. Disagree

5. Strongly disagree

Support from the co-worker is helpful to get motivated	
Strongly agree	16%
Agree	39%
Neutral	2%
Disagree	30%
Strongly disagree	13%

FIGURE 5.16

Interpretation

16% of the respondents strongly agree that the support from the co-worker is helpful to get motivated while 13% of the respondents strongly disagree with this statement. 2% of the respondents are neutral. 39% of the respondents agree while 30% of the respondents disagree that the support from the co-worker is helpful to get motivated

17. Company recognizes and acknowledge your work

- 1. Strongly agree
- 2. Agree
- 3. Neutral
- 4. Disagree
- 5. Strongly disagree

TABLE 5.17

Company recognizes and acknowledge your work	
Strongly agree	2%
Agree	15%
Neutral	7%
Disagree	58%
Strongly disagree	18%

FIGURE 5.17

Interpretation

From the above analysis, it is clear that majority of the respondent either strongly disagree (18%) or only disagree (58%) that the company recognizes and acknowledge their work. 7% of the respondents are neutral. 2% of the respondents strongly agree while 15% of the respondents only agree that the company recognizes and acknowledge their work.

18. Which of the following factor motivates you the most?

1. Salary increase
2. Promotion
3. Leave
4. Motivational talks
5. Recognition

TABLE 5.18

Factors that motivates	
Salary Increase	60%
Promotion	15%
Leave	7%
Motivational Talks	10%
Recognition	8%

FIGURE 5.18

Interpretation

Majority of the respondents (60%) think that only increase in their salary by the organization can motivates them the most while 15% of the respondents think that it is the Promotion by the organization that motivates them. 7% of the respondents say Leave while 10% of the respondents think that Motivational talks motivates them the most. However, 8% of the respondents believe that it is the recognition that motivates them the most.

19. Do you think that the incentives and other benefits will influence your performance?

- 1. Influence
- 2. Does not influence
- 3. No opinion

TABLE 5.19

Do you think that incentives and other Benefits will influence your performance	
Influence	75%
Does not influence	20%
No Opinion	5%

FIGURE 5.19

Interpretation

75% of the respondents believe that Incentives and other benefits will influence their performance while 20% of the respondents does not believe that Incentives and other benefits will influence their performance. 5% of the respondents do not have any opinion on this statement.

20. Does the management involves you in decision making which are connected to your department?

1. Yes
2. No
3. Occasionally

TABLE 5.20

Does the management involves you in decision making which are connected to your department	
Yes	25%
No	68%
Occasionally	7%

FIGURE 5.20

Interpretation

68% of the respondents believe that the management does not involve them in decision making which are connected to their department while 25% of the respondents agree that the management involves them in decision making which are connected to their department. However, there are 7% of the respondents who believe that the management occasionally involve them in decision making which are connected to their department.

Tabulation Of Questionnaire Response

Q.No	OPTIONS					TOTAL Questions
	1	2	3	4	5	
1	10	65	23	2	No	100
2	20	65	15	No	No	100
3	56	24	12	8	No	100
4	5	35	44	12	4	100
5	2	10	25	46	17	100
6	68	24	8	No	No	100
7	3	19	25	35	18	100
8	2	25	15	48	10	100
9	10	35	20	28	7	100
10	20	45	5	19	11	100
11	3	10	10	59	18	100
12	38	62	No	No	No	100
13	15	46	5	28	6	100
14	19	36	3	30	12	100
15	9	19	5	65	2	100
16	16	39	2	30	13	100
17	2	15	7	58	18	100
18	60	15	7	10	8	100
19	75	20	5	No	No	100
20	25	68	7	No	No	100
TOTAL	458	677	243	478	144	2000
% to TOTAL	23	34	12	24	7	100

TABLE 6.1

6.0.FINDINGS OF RESEARCH

1. Most of the respondent (i.e 65%) are between the age group of 30-39 years while only 2% of the respondent are above the group of 50 years and above. 10% of the respondents are under the age group of 30 years while 23% of the respondents are between the age group of 40-49 years.

2. 65% of the respondents are completed graduation while 20% of the respondents are below graduates. However, only 15% of the respondents are Post graduates
3. 56% of the respondents are working in the organization above 20 years while 24% of the respondents are working in the organization between 15-20 years. 12% of the respondents are working in the organization between 10-15 years while 8% of the respondents are working in the organization for less than 10 years.
4. 5% of the respondents are highly satisfied with the support from HR department while 4% of the respondents are highly dissatisfied. 44% of the respondents are neutral while 12% of the respondents are dissatisfied and 35% are satisfied with the support from HR department.
5. 46% of the respondents disagree that the management is really interested in motivating the employees while 10% of the respondents agree with this statement. 25% of the respondents are neutral while 17% of the respondents strongly disagree that the management is really interested in motivating the employees while only 2% of the respondents strongly agree to this statement.
6. 68% of the respondents believe that only financial incentives motivates them while 24% of the respondents are in favor of Non-financial incentives. However, only 8% of the respondents believe that both types of incentives motivates them.

7. 3% of the respondents are highly satisfied with the incentives provided by the organization while 18% of the respondents are highly dissatisfied with the incentives scheme of the organization. 19% of the respondents are satisfied while 35% of the respondents dislike the incentive scheme provided by the organization. 25% of the respondents are neutral.

8. 2% of the respondents strongly agree with the reasonable periodical increase in salary by organization while 10% of the respondents strongly disagree with this statement. 25% of the respondents agree that the organization provide reasonable periodical salary increase while 48% of the respondents disagree with this statement. 15% of the respondents are neutral to this statement.

9. 30% of the respondents agree that the job security exist in the company while 1% of the respondents strongly disagree with this statement. 17% of the respondents are neutral. 12% of the respondents disagree that the job security exist in the company while majority of the respondents (i.e 40%) agree that the job security exist In the organization

10. 20% of the respondents strongly agree that good relationship with co-workers exist in the organization while 11% of the respondents strongly disagree with this statement. Majority of the respondents (i.e 45%) only agree that good relationship with co-workers exist in the organization while 19% of the respondents disagree with this statement. 5% of the respondents are neutral.

11. Majority of the respondents (i.e 59%) disagree that the organization has the effective performance appraisal system while 10% of the respondents agree with this statement. 10% of the respondents are neutral and they neither agree nor disagree with the statement. However, there are only 3% of the respondents who strongly agree that the organization has the effective performance appraisal system while 18% of the respondents strongly disagree with this statement.
12. 62% of the respondents believe that they do not have the opportunity to develop their skills and abilities while 38% of the respondents think that they have the opportunity to develop their skills and abilities.
13. 15% of the respondents strongly agree that the organization has effective promotional opportunities while 6% of the respondents strongly disagree with this statement. However, there are 46% of the respondents who only agree with this statement while 28% of the respondents only disagree with this statement. There are 5% of the respondents who neither agree nor disagree that the organization has effective promotional opportunities.
14. 19% of the respondents strongly agree whereas only 12% of the respondents strongly disagree that the safety measures adopted by the organization are good. 3% of the respondents are neutral. Majority of the respondents (i.e 36%) agree with this statement while 30% of the respondents disagree that good safety measures are adopted in the organization.

15. 65% of the respondents disagree that the performance appraisal activities of the organization are helpful to get motivated while 19% of the respondents agree with this statement. However, there are 9% of the respondents who strongly agree that the performance appraisal activities of the organization are helpful to get motivated while 2% of the respondents strongly disagree with this statement. 5% of the respondents are neutral.
16. 16% of the respondents strongly agree that the support from the co-worker is helpful to get motivated while 13% of the respondents strongly disagree with this statement. 2% of the respondents are neutral. 39% of the respondents agree while 30% of the respondents disagree that the support from the co-worker is helpful to get motivated.
17. Majority of the respondent either strongly disagree (18%) or only disagree (58%) that the company recognizes and acknowledge their work. 7% of the respondents are neutral. 2% of the respondents strongly agree while 15% of the respondents only agree that the company recognizes and acknowledge their work.
18. Majority of the respondents (60%) think that only increase in their salary by the organization can motivates them the most while 15% of the respondents think that it is the Promotion by the organization that motivates them. 7% of the respondents say Leave while 10% of the respondents think that Motivational talks motivates them the most. However, 8% of the respondents believe that it is the recognition that motivates them the most.

19. 75% of the respondents believe that Incentives and other benefits will influence their performance while 20% of the respondents does not believe that Incentives and other benefits will influence their performance. 5% of the respondents do not have any opinion on this statement.

20. 68% of the respondents believe that the management does not involve them in decision making which are connected to their department while 25% of the respondents agree that the management involves them in decision making which are connected to their department. However, there are 7% of the respondents who believe that the management occasionally involve them in decision making which are connected to their department.

6.1.CONCLUSIONS

Recognition was found to be a contributing factor in motivating employees, and the company with appropriate system for identifying the employee skills , abilities and talents will help make employees feel more involved and appreciated. If employees have a greater respect for their company and are satisfied with the way information is relayed to them, they will be more motivated in the workplace and their work will improve as a result. The amount of communication between managers and employees is very critical, and overall employee motivation can depend on how much they feel the Officers cares about them as individuals and values their work as well. There is definitely room for improvement in the quality of work at the company and overall performance.

Mastering a job is a strong motivational factor, as are salary and other financial incentives (bonuses, etc.), but many employees like to seek

advancement in the company. These forms of long-term incentives actually provide more productivity from the workers, because they are actually working toward something instead of just trying to maintain it.

Long-term incentives such as opportunity for promotion, along with other like incentives, are beneficial in influencing more overall productivity. Also, short-term financial incentives could give motivation to only do what has been successful in the past and not to be creative.

Employees at the company want job security, good relation with co workers ,good safety measures and support from their co workers in the the company . They want to be secured and good working environment With 40% of the respondents feel they are secured at their current positions and many believe that support from co workers in the company is insufficient, it is very rational to believe that an increase in interpersonal relationships and mutual cooperation among co workers will lead to an increase in overall employee motivation.

The research and findings illustrate that competitive wages are a strong motivational factor, especially for the lower-income demographic of the company. They are less pleased with management and the company, which helps lead to their comparatively low motivation levels. They desire a higher income but are often forced to settle for non-financial incentives when their wishes are not granted. That makes them value these incentives more highly than the “higher income” demographic values them, but that is because they do not have a high income to motivate them and help them forget about other forms of motivation.

The study showed that short-term financial incentives are not necessarily conducive to innovation. Short-term incentives motivate employees to do the work the way they have always done it, and not to try to find a different or more efficient method of completing the job. Non financial incentives such as achieving recognition and credit, seeing the impact an employee's work has, mastering a certain position, and flexibility of scheduling can greatly influence motivation. The extent of their effectiveness in this company is limited, though, which means the company and the managers need to make a greater effort to incorporate incentives that are important to and valued by the average employee, such as these.

The respondents of the questionnaire in the "low-income" demographic were less motivated and were slightly more critical of the quality of communication in the company, management styles, and the company's effort to offer achievable and worthwhile incentives. They felt more strongly than the higher-income demographic about the ability of financial incentives, achieving recognition and credit, and gaining proficiency at their job to motivate them to do their best work. This is primarily because they earn a lower wage and feel the need to compensate for their lack of pay by feeling more strongly about and putting more emphasis on the ideas of incentives and other motivational factors in the workplace, whether they are actually receiving them or not. By receiving a higher wage, these employees' overall motivation levels would increase because they would no longer be lacking that important motivational factor and having to compensate.

While employees find their pay to be an undeniably vital aspect of their jobs, it cannot stand on its own as the sole incentive provided by the company. Though important, financial incentives were actually found to be less motivating than the employee simply gaining proficiency at their job, or the employee's work having a noticeable effect on the company. Where financial rewards might be excessive, inappropriate, or unaffordable, being praised or personally thanked can facilitate the employee's desire to have a greater, more meaningful effect on the company.

6.2.RECOMMENDATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

With the data from the questionnaire collected and analyzed, and with the recommendations drawn from the findings of the study, the company will be better able to understand what it can do to motivate its employees more effectively and increase morale in the workplace. Recommendations to the company based on this study include: raising the wages of the lower income employees at the company, promoting more from within the company, encouraging better and more frequent communication between managers and employees, making sure employees are receiving significant credit and recognition for their great work, and offering more opportunities for employees to increase their skill-sets and to master their respective positions. If there is a greater level of understanding and cohesion between employees and managers, and if the right types of incentives are added to effectively motivate employees, productivity and revenues will increase, and the company as a whole will greatly benefit.

The following recommendations are made to the company based on the findings and conclusions of this study on employee motivation and its most influencing factors, for the purpose of enhancing the overall level of employee motivation in the company and increasing work efficiency.

1. Provide more competitive wages to the “low-income” segment of the company.
2. Increase the possibility of employee promotion in the company by promoting from within rather than recruiting fresh candidates from outside.
3. Encourage more frequent communication between managers and their employees, and implement team-building and communication exercises to help strengthen the relationship and trust between the two groups.
4. Put effort into ensuring that employees are properly credited and receive recognition for the good work they do in their respective positions.
5. Offer more opportunities for job advancement and education, in order to allow employees to completely master their respective positions.
6. Provide necessary training to the employees in their respective fields periodically to develop the skills & abilities, to help in decision making and to motivate them for new advancements and challenges.
7. A periodical meeting of all the employees of the concerned division/section will provide a homely working environment & builds a good relationship among Line & staff persons and also resolves many HR conflicts.

6.3.Future Scope of Study

1. The future research can be carried out on a large sample size and with reference to different district level dairies of KMF in Karnataka State . It can

be compared with other programs of KMF and find out the differences and similarities with it.

2.The future research can be carried out on a larger sample at Other Co-operative Federations like Co-operative Banks & other co-operative organizations in Karnataka state and find out the differences and similarities with it.

3. The future research can also be carried out on a larger sample at other Co-operative Milk Federations in India like AMUL in Gujarat State and find out the differences and similarities with it.

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APPENDICE 1: QUESTIONNAIRE

1. Age Group:

1. Under 30
2. 30-39
3. 40-49
4. 50 and over

2. Highest Qualification

1. Below Graduation
2. Graduation
3. Post Graduation

3. Length of service

1. Above 20 yerars
2. 15-20 years
3. 10-15 years
4. Less than 10 years

4. Are you satisfied with the support from the HR department?

1. Highly satisfied
2. Satisfied
3. Neutral

4. Dissatisfied
5. Highly Dissatisfied
5. Management is really interested in motivating the employees?
 1. Strongly agree
 2. Agree
 3. Neutral
 4. Disagree
 5. Strongly disagree
6. Which type of incentives motivates you more?
 1. Financial incentives
 2. Non-financial incentives
 3. Both
7. How far you are satisfied with the incentives provided by the organization?
 1. Highly satisfied
 2. Satisfied
 3. Neutral
 4. Dissatisfied
 5. Highly Dissatisfied
8. You get reasonable periodical increase in salary
 1. Strongly agree
 2. Agree
 3. Neutral
 4. Disagree
 5. Strongly disagree

9. Job security exist in the company
 1. Strongly agree
 2. Agree
 3. Neutral
 4. Disagree
 5. Strongly disagree
10. Good relationship with co-workers exists in the organization
 1. Strongly agree
 2. Agree
 3. Neutral
 4. Disagree
 5. Strongly disagree
11. Organization has the effective performance appraisal system
 1. Strongly agree
 2. Agree
 3. Neutral
 4. Disagree
 5. Strongly disagree
12. Do you have the opportunity to further develop your skills and abilities.
 1. Yes
 2. No
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 1. Strongly agree
 2. Agree
 3. Neutral
 4. Disagree
 5. Strongly disagree

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 1. Strongly agree
 2. Agree
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 2. Agree
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 4. Disagree
 5. Strongly disagree

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 3. Neutral
 4. Disagree
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2. Promotion
3. Leave
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5. Recognition

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1. Influence
2. Does not influence
3. No opinion

20. Does the management involves you in decision making which are connected to your department?

1. Yes
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KARNATAKA MILK FEDERATION LTD ,CENTRAL OFFICE,BANGALORE

3 TIER STRUCTURE OF KMF

DIFFERENT VARIETIES OF MILK AND MILK PRODUCTS MANUFACTURED UNDER "NANDINI" BRAND AND MARKETED BY KMF

LOCATION OF DIFFERENT DAIRIES , UNION OFFICES, CATTLE FEED PLANTS , PRODUCT PLANTS, TRAINING INSTITUTES AND MEGA DARY OF KARNATAKA MILK FEDERATION LTD, BANGALORE

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